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LEA
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1. Introduction

This report is Deliverable 3.1 connected to Task 3.1 in the WP3 of the LEA project. The leader of the work package is Otto von Guericke University, and the deliverable was compiled by the task leader INNOVA Észak-Alföld Nonprofit Kft. Deliverable 3.1 is part of MS1. Task 3.1 enables a better mutual understanding between the end users, the procurers and the suppliers that can facilitate innovative procurement in education.

1.1 Purpose of the report

Task 3.1 and D3.1 aim to identify the procurement arena of Education in Europe in order to map levels of procurement in different countries and barriers of legislation standards. This information contributes to the effective work with demand policies and innovative procurement on EU level in the LEA project. D3.1 is the analysis of learning technology procurement in the countries of the European Union and the identification of the demand side barriers. The deliverable will be used to understand how to use the LEA Network with a broader approach and it will be used to prepare the PPI later in the project.

1.2 Methodology

D3.1 is mainly based on the analysis of white papers and reports. A questionnaire was also conducted by INNOVA and filled out by LEA partners. LEA Consortium has deeper knowledge about the levels of procurement and countries and barriers of legislation standards in Austria, Belgium, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Portugal, Spain and Sweden.

Desk research was an effective method to collect this information as there are official documents, reports and statistics made for the European Union and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). These reports summarize different sectors and their structure in each country. From these documents many information could be utilized to map the education technology procurement systems in the countries, and as is a trustworthy way of research, helps to improve quality on the content that will be published on European Commission

and OECD websites. These documents can be downloaded free of charge, thus the research is based on cost-effectively obtained reliable and relevant data.

A questionnaire was used as a structured technique for collecting primary data from LEA partnering countries. It is generally a series of written questions for which the respondents have to provide answers (see annex 1). The option for online questionnaire was used due to different locations of the respondents for the purpose that the data would be more convenient to collect. The questionnaire provided a systematic way to analyse the information. In the analysis, some descriptive statistical information and figures about the respondents' characteristics were included into the analysis.

The main goal was to prepare an accurate, well-designed questionnaire in order to motivate the respondents to give relevant and complete information. The questions have been edited to not have a manipulative impact on the answers. In this way, reliable information has been obtained from the respondents. The questions of the survey are attached as an Annex to this report (Annex 1).

Open-ended questions were used in case of the indication of the decision-making organization in case of ICT procurement, because every country is different, and there are types of organizations which are only relevant and valid for only one country, thus we were not able to predict the answer possibilities. In all the cases, from previous experience or knowledge about the partner/country, it was possible to indicate the possible answers; closed-ended questions were used with multiple answer possibilities. There were some closed-ended questions used with two possible opposite outcomes (e.g. Do the primary/secondary schools have the right to decide what kind of educational technology tool to purchase?). However, in this type of questions, a plus option was also given (other) to provide the opportunity to express that the respondent does not have enough information to provide an answer. This was necessary in order to prevent the distortion of the result and invalid results. It was restricted that the answer is acceptable if the respondents specify what the "other" option exactly covers.

Moreover, in the case of all questions and answers, space for comments was provided to give the possibility to add explanations. There are cases when it is hard to decide which answer is the most applicable, and with the comments, respondents were given the opportunity to explain, why they choose the answer and they could add further information in connection with the answer.

Ranking question was also used: in one question respondents were asked to indicate the importance of listed factors. The indication was between 1- not important at all and 4- extremely important. In the case of all factors only one answer could be chosen, however, it was possible to add further factors and indicate their importance. The question was about the decisive factors in the choice of education technology tools, and the list of factors was compiled based on experience from the IMAILE project.

2. General description of the public procurement and education system in the member states of the European Union

2.1 Introduction

In the European Union, all countries have their own education systems and methods of government. In general, the government method can be centralized, decentralized and semi-centralized. For mapping, the European Education arena, all countries and their education government system are analysed. In this report, the decision making processes and the parties taking part in the decision making will be described.

The European Union has 28 members at the moment: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom.

2.2 Austria

In Austria regarding the governance of education, a federal structure is being maintained with very strong central competencies. The governance and administration of the education system are divided between central and provincial authorities. At the central level, the Federal Ministry of Education (BMB) is in charge of the legislative issues and the curricula in compulsory education including public compulsory schools, vocational education, training institutions at the secondary level and private schools. Its authority includes the teacher service, wage, salary and retirement policy and administration. For the higher education institutions, the main authority is the Federal Ministry of Science, Research and Economy (BWF). Other bodies that help the authorities in the governance of the education system are:

- the Agency for Quality Assurance and Accreditation Austria is in charge of the quality assurance of higher education institutions

- the Federal Institute for Research on Education, Innovation and Development of the Austrian School System carries out the necessary evaluations by collecting information about students, teachers and schools
- the Austrian Science Board provides support to central and local authorities regarding tertiary education
- other stakeholders such as students' unions, teachers' unions

At the province level, provincial authorities are in charge of pre-primary schools and they have to provide staff for general compulsory schools. Their responsibility includes the implementation of the federal framework of legislation.

At local level municipalities are obliged to maintain school buildings for compulsory general education. Schools have the right to make the majority of the decisions regarding curriculum, but they have got lower autonomy in decisions regarding resource allocation. They play an important role in the establishment of disciplinary and student assessment policies.

Similar to the governance the funding of education is also divided between the central and the provincial level. The funding mechanism depends on the type of the school:

- federal schools (including academic secondary schools and vocational upper secondary schools and colleges) get funding directly from the central government
- provincial schools (including general compulsory schools) are financed by provinces and municipalities, but a big share of this fundings comes originally from the federal budget.

Both types of schools have a very low level of financial autonomy, the head of the school can barely decide how to use the allocated funds.

In Austria, public procurement processes are carried out at all levels of government. An important share of purchases is being centralised by the Federal Procurement Agency (BBG), which is also in charge of the e-procurement system. For federal bodies, it is compulsory to purchase through the BBG, however federal states, municipalities, and public owned-bodies can choose to purchase approximately 270 000 standardized products and services through the Federal

Procurement Agency. The aim behind the central body was to create savings during the procurement procedures and in 2013 the BBG procured goods of 1.2 billion EUR with generating savings of 253 million EUR.

Municipalities have the right to found limited liability companies in order to do joint procurements. Many inter-municipal co-operations are working now in order to support centralised procurement management at local level.

The supervisory role in the public procurement system in Austria is fulfilled by the Austrian Court of Audit. Its tasks are to supervise the economy, efficiency and effectiveness of public procurement expenditure at the federal state and also local levels. It gathers its findings into thematic and annual reports that are publicly available.

2.3 Belgium

The Education Policy Outlook compiled for OECD describes the governance system of education in Belgium. There is a different system in the Flemish community, in the French community and in the German-speaking community. These communities are shown in the map below:

Figure 1 : Communities in Belgium
Source: <https://www.flemishparliament.eu/about-the-flemish-parliament/structure-belgium>

The Federal State is responsible for the age range of compulsory education, sets the required regulations for educational staff and establishes the minimum requirements for qualifications. However, the three different communities have got their own education governing system and established the dedicated bodies/authorities.

In the Flemish Community, policy coordination is performed by the Department for Education and Training. The implementation is the responsibility of one of the three autonomous agencies: Agency for Educational Services for elementary, secondary, part-time autistic education, student guidance centres – AgODI, Agency for Higher Education, Adult Education, Qualifications and Study Allowances – AHOVOKS and Agency for Educational Infrastructure – AGIO. AGIO manages the design, planning and building as well as the renovation of school buildings. Usually, these works are carried out on grants both in the case of public and private schools. The Flemish Community established a student guidance system with centres specialized in multi-disciplinary, student-oriented consultancy and support for students, parents and schools.

In the French Community, there is one public body – the General Administration of Education (AGE) - with six directorates being responsible for education. The administrative body also provides general services, and there are sections being responsible for compulsory education, educational staffs, scientific research, school supervisions, general policy steering, coordination, design and social relations. Walloon region authorities are responsible for school transport and they maintain school buildings together with the French Community authorities.

In the German-speaking Community, education and academic research are the responsibilities of the Minister of Education. Another department controls and manages extracurricular training. Schools have the right to set their own curricula, but core learning outcomes are legislatively determined, and the curricula should support the achievement of these outcomes. Schools are also entitled to recruit their own staff on the basis of the corresponding legal regulations.

In Belgium, schools are classified into three categories, based on the source of funding and structure of management:

- publicly funded schools being under the direct authority of the Community
- grant-aided schools being publicly managed for example by cities or municipalities
- grant-aided schools being privately managed (for example religious schools, schools with specific training methodologies)

There are school boards that are responsible for managing one or more schools. These school boards usually belong to an umbrella organisation, which provides support for them and represents them in discussions with the government.

In Belgium, the majority (95% in 2013) of expenditure on educational institutions are financed from public sources. With this share of public-financed expenditure, Belgium surpasses the OECD average (84%). Education is financed by the above mentioned three Communities, however, the German-speaking Community receives funding from the Province of Luxembourg as well. This funding is received particularly for special education needs.

In the French Community, significant investment has been made since 2011 in order to promote innovative teaching skills and to develop strong ICT skills among students. In the framework of these investments, Internet connections have been provided for Walloon schools with the cost of 35 million Euro, and multimedia equipment w purchased for schools in the Brussel Capital Region (with a total value of 6 million Euro). Between 2014 and 2019 an initiative called "Fiber to the School" has been implemented for providing high-speed Internet connection to all secondary schools (with investing 10 million Euro).

The public procurement system due to the political and administration system of the country is connected to the three regions. At the federal level the following bodies are responsible for the procurement system:

- the Federal Public Service Chancellery of the Prime Minister – prepares, coordinates and monitors the legislation regarding public procurement

processes, and the development of e-procurement as well as the adjusting of the national law to the EU directives

- the Central Procurement Body for the Federal Services- it consists of altogether 11 units, and each unit is specialized in one of the following areas: insurance, fuel, hygiene, IT, furniture, office supplies, telecommunication, shrinks and snacks, cars and light commercial vehicles. This body manages contracts on behalf of the federal state.
- the Purchasing Advice and Policy Unit – it provides advice to purchasing departments of the federal institutions.

The Commission for Public Procurement is a specialised advisory body that includes representatives from the federal authority, federated entities, public corporations, supervision bodies, and representatives of businesses and trade unions.

The financial control is exercised by the Belgian Court of Audit regarding the public federal institutions, communities, regional authorities and provincial authorities as well.

The responsible bodies for the review of public procurement procedures are the Belgian Council of State and the civil courts. These authorities can issue a penalty, suspension, cancellation of the contract, and the decision of the Belgian Council of State is not subject to appeal.

2.4 Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, education is the responsibility of the Ministry of Education and Science. Education is regulated by the Public Education Act that has changed in 2002 when the education of children with special educational needs in pre-schools was integrated into general education schools and vocational schools.

The major objective of the reform of the Bulgarian education system was to adapt to the European standards and to harmonize the educational process with the processes in Western Europe.

Bulgarian schools are well-equipped with traditional audio-visual tools (for example maps, charts, globes) and technical appliances such as overhead projectors, TV sets, cassette-recorders and slide-projectors. However, there is a strong and urgent need to update information technology tools and equipment in order to create the compliance with the current education material and the needs of the 21st century. Bulgarian teachers are quite open to new methods and technologies, but the financial sources are relatively poor to update to modern ICT tools.

Bulgaria dedicated one of their operational programmes (Operational Programme “Science and Education for Smart Growth”) to the development of science and education between 2014 and 2020. The programme has been financed from European and national funds and has been managed by the Ministry of Education and Science with a total budget of 1.37 billion BGN. The Programme has three main objectives:

- To increase the share of investment in science and research to 1.5% of GDP
- To reduce the share of early school leavers below 11%
- To increase the share of higher education graduates among 30-34-year-olds to 36%.

The public procurement system of Bulgaria has always been rather centralised. In order to increase local control by decentralising budget, the number of contracting authorities has risen in recent years. As a result, more procurement contracts became controlled by mayors, school administrators and other municipal officials who often have a lack of knowledge and experience regarding public procurement processes. In Bulgaria, public procurement is very complex and continuously changing both in legal and regulatory terms. There have been many actions taken in order to reduce and prevent corruption and to strengthen management and control systems in the process of public procurement. Therefore, ex-ante controls performed by the Public procurement agency was introduced according to the bidding documentation for EU sponsored projects.

In Bulgaria, the main body responsible for public procurement is the PPA – Public Procurement Agency. PPA is an independent body but it belongs organizationally

to the Ministry of Economy. The Public Procurement Agency is responsible for the following activities:

- to draft laws on public procurement
- to give methodological and other forms of guidance
- to perform mandatory ex-ante controls for all ESI Funds co-funded procurement processes with a value above 1.3 million EUR and for contracts of non EU funded works with a value of over 5 million EUR
- to monitor and analyse procurement markets
- to alert supervision authorities on possible irregularities
- to maintain the PPR – Public Procurement Register (electronic database with information about public procurement procedures)

The purchasing body for central administration is the Central Financing and Contracting Unit Directorate within the Ministry of Finance. In Bulgaria's procurement system the Commission for the Protection of Competition (CPC) is the first instance review body examining and deciding on claims of irregularities in public procurement processes. It also has the right to interrupt the procedure in case of non-compliance and impose sanctions.

The NAO – National Audit Office performs independent audits of national public finance for legality, efficiency and effectiveness regularly auditing contracting authorities both at central and local levels. NAO has limited rights to impose sanctions as it can only forward its findings to the State Financial Inspection Agency. This agency also belongs to the Ministry of Finance and is responsible for ensuring the protection of public financial interests. Therefore it carries out inspections of the budget and financial-economic and accounting activities of public bodies with the right of imposing sanctions.

2.5 Croatia

In the Republic of Croatia, the Ministry of Science and Education performs the majority of tasks regarding preschool education, primary education and

secondary education. These tasks include administrative tasks, developing the National Curriculum, approving textbooks, introducing regulations, standards and other requirements, fostering the development of the school system. The Ministry is also responsible for conducting inspections, establishing educational institutions, supervising the legal aspects of educational institutions' work, providing funding and facilities for educational work, enabling children, young adults and adults to acquire technical skills and competencies and supporting organizations investing in education.

The Ministry of Science and Education is responsible for some tasks regarding higher education as well:

- development of higher education
- implementation of national strategies
- implementation of higher education programmes
- providing funding and facilities for higher education institutions
- monitoring the activities of higher education organizations and preparing reports about them
- improvement of student standard
- monitoring success rates of study programmes
- subsidization of study costs
- administrative supervision of higher education institutions
- administering the implementation of the Croatian Qualifications Framework
- administering the Registry of Higher Education Institutions and the Registry of School Programmes
- managing databases on higher education
- fostering lifelong learning and higher education for adults

The Ministry of Science and Education is responsible for several other tasks, from which the following are relevant for the Learntech Accelerator project:

- development of science, technology and innovation system
- application of scientific achievements in certain fields
- to foster technological development in the Republic of Croatia

- monitoring and establishing scientific co-operations with foreign countries and international organizations

Regarding the public procurement processes in the Republic of Croatia, the Directorate for the Public Procurement System is the central organization belonging to the Ministry of Economy. The Ministry of Finance is responsible for concessions. The Public-Private Partnership Agency was founded to be responsible for Public-Private Partnerships and the State Commission for the Supervision of Public Procurement Procedures performs reviews. In the Republic of Croatia the following institutions, organizations can be contracting authorities:

- state bodies of the Republic of Croatia
- local and regional self-government units
- bodies governed by public law (legal entities established for the specific purpose of meeting the needs of general interest)
- associations established by one of the above-mentioned bodies
- persons which are not contracting authorities but are directly subsidized by contracting authorities by more than 50% of the procurement value
- persons operating in the fields of water supply, energy, transport and postal service

In the public procurement system of the Republic of Croatia, a major problem is that the major deciding factor is still the lowest price instead of the economically most advantageous tender.

2.6 Cyprus

In Cyprus, the Ministry of Education and Culture (MoEC) is responsible for the administration of public schools and the supervision of private schools regarding pre-primary, primary, secondary level and educational institutions of post-secondary, tertiary level and universities. The Ministry of Education and Culture has to prepare the educational budget, draft new laws regarding education and ensure the implementation of existing laws. MoEC is also responsible for developing

and implementing education policy in line with the declared vision of the government at national level.

The particular tasks of the Ministry of Education and Culture are:

- to develop strategic goals and programs in order to fulfil the vision of the government
- to prepare annual operational plans
- to monitor the progress of achieving the goals
- to support educational institutions in implementing the programs
- to be responsible for the continuous professional development of teachers and principals
- to be responsible for the inspection of schools
- to implement and supervise research related to education and culture

The expenditure regarding Education can be seen in the graph below in EUR by categories in the years 2014, 2015 and 2016.

Figure 2 : Expenditure regarding education in Cyprus 2014-2016 (source: Ministry of Education and Culture: Annual report – 2016)

The graph shows that there is a hectic movement of the expenditure: in 2015 it was lower than the data of 2014, but for 2016 the total amount increased by more than 5 000 EUR compared to 2014 and by almost 10 000 EUR compared to 2015. The most important developments have been implemented regarding the school premises. School equipment represents a very low share among the expenditure. According to the annual report of the Ministry of Education and Culture, there has been a current school building programme in 2016 with improvement and construction of school building premises.

The public procurement system of Cyprus has a decentralized character with contracting authorities being responsible for their own tenders. However, the legislative and review body is centralized at the state level. The centralised body dealing with matters regarding public procurement in Cyprus is the Public Procurement Directorate (PPD) within the Cyprus Treasury. In the country, there are approximately 700 contracting authorities. The Public Procurement Directorate has got the following tasks and responsibilities:

- to draft public procurement legislation
- to ensure the implementation of public procurement legislation
- to support contracting authorities for proper implementation of the procurement rules
- to carry out checks on contracting authorities in order to ensure compliance with procurement law
- to issue compliance certificates to contracting authorities in case of projects with a value below the EU threshold

There are several bodies for implementing public procurement procedures for contracting authorities at the state level. These bodies have different expertise on the basis of which they are appointed to implement the different procurement procedures. The Department of Information Technology Services is responsible for purchasing IT products, the Department of Purchasing and Supply is responsible for procedures regarding common use products, while the Department of

Electromechanical Services is responsible for purchases of electromechanical products and for the Printing Office.

For the overview and control of public procurement procedure in Cyprus, two other central bodies are appointed (besides the Public Procurement Directorate): Audit Office of the Republic of Cyprus and the Internal Audit Service of the Republic of Cyprus. The Audit Office of the Republic of Cyprus performs external controls of the execution of the national budget. It supervises all the public-funded activities including public procurement documents, procedures and award decisions. The Audit Office of the Republic of Cyprus is an independent body and it publishes its findings in an annual report but it does not have the right to issue sanctions or to launch judicial proceedings. It can notify the Attorney General if it finds out any violations in the procurement area. The Attorney General has the right to commence judicial proceedings where in his opinion there is a legal issue. The Internal Audit Office of the Republic of Cyprus implements internal audits of public organisations and EU-funded programmes of Cyprus including public procurement procedures.

Regarding public procurement decisions, appeals can be issued with the independent Tenders Review Authority (TRA) of Cyprus. TRA is responsible for maintaining equal treatment, transparency and non-discrimination in the procurement process. The Tenders Review Authority has the right to cancel or amend award decisions.

2.7 Czech Republic

In the Czech Republic the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (MEYS) is responsible for determining national education policy and long-term policy objectives that guide the educational system and all-level education (pre-school, primary school, secondary school, vocational and technical education, upper secondary school, higher professional schools and adult education). Besides the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport, there are other central bodies taking part in the governing system of education in the Czech Republic:

- the Czech School Inspectorate (CSI) is responsible for monitoring and analysing the education system and its quality (without higher education institutions)
- the National Institute of Education (NUV) is responsible for developing information on issues regarding education levels from pre-primary through upper secondary, vocational and technical education
- NUV is also responsible for guidance and counselling of education
- NUV is appointed to formulate the framework of education programmes and to guide the development of school programmes
- the National Institute for Further Education focuses on in-service teacher training
- the Centre for Higher Education Studies is responsible for developing policy and strategy for higher education
- there is a continuous collaboration between the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports and other ministries (e.g. the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs) on several cross-sectoral issues
- several advisory bodies were founded (e.g. associations of teachers, an association of employers', etc.) in order to implement negotiations regarding the national educational programme, the framework educational programmes and long-term policy objectives at national and regional levels

The organisation of pre-primary and compulsory education (between 6 and 15 years old) is the responsibility of the municipalities. There are many authorities having the right to establish schools: ministries, regions, municipalities, religious societies, churches and other legal entities. There are fourteen regional governments being responsible for governing upper secondary and tertiary professional schools in their own region including the steering of the educational objectives being implemented in the educational institutions.

In 2003 schools were given more autonomy to make decisions regarding their operation. According to the following figure, 68% of the decisions are taken by

schools, 28% is taken at the local or regional level and the remaining 4% is taken at the central level.

Figure 3 : Decisions taken in public lower secondary schools at each level of government (2010)
 (Source: OECD (2012), Education at a Glance 2012: OECD Indicators, OECD Publishing, Paris, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/eag-2012-en>)

In each school, a school board has to be established in order to allow participation of parents, students, education staff and the general public.

Higher education institutions, on the other hand, are autonomous and they are accredited by the Accreditation Commission. These institutions are represented by the Council of Higher Education Institutions and the Czech Rectors' Conference at the national level.

Between 2011 and 2015, the Long-Term Plan for Education was implemented in order to improve the quality and efficiency of the education system and to improve its international competitiveness. In the recent years the Czech Republic has increased its investment in education, and as in most of the OECD Countries, a large share of the expenditure in educational institutions comes from public sources.

The financing is mainly determined by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports, while regions and municipalities can add extra funds. National funds are allocated

to the regions on a per-capita basis for schools' costs such as salaries and learning materials. Regions and municipalities allocate these funds to schools, while the school leaders are appointed to be responsible for the financial management of the school. For students with special needs, schools get extra funding on a per-student basis, and they can apply for extra funding in the following cases:

- for students who live in a socio-economically disadvantaged situation
- additional funding for extra materials
- additional funding for personnel costs

Private schools can also receive state funding for teachers' salaries and running costs: for pre-primary and primary schools this subsidy is up to 100%, while in secondary schools up to 90%. Church schools are fully supported by the national budget.

The Education for Competitiveness Operational Programme (2007-2013) offered grants based on project applications. The main objective was to increase the use of ICT in education in order to meet the needs of the schools. The other priority of this operational programme was the continuing education of teachers.

The public procurement system in the Czech Republic is decentralized, all the contracting authorities manage their own procurement without any central control.

The Ministry for Regional Development (MoRD) proposes legislation and implements the regulations in connection with public procurement procedures. It also provides support and helps for contracting authorities and manages the online Public Procurement and Concessions Portal. It is also responsible for the Information System on Public Procurement.

There is no central purchasing body in the Czech Republic, but it is allowed for contracting authorities to implement joint purchasing. The lists of commodities that can only be purchased jointly is an effort by the government to insert some sort of

centralization in the system. There are two oversight bodies between which the responsibility of the control is shared:

- the Office for the Protection of Competition (OPC) supervises the public procurement procedures in terms of compliance to the legislation and it is authorized to impose any penalties, sanctions, and even bans in case of any breaches
- the Supreme Audit Office (SAO) performs external reviews in terms of compliance with the regulations and it forwards its findings to the Parliament, the administration and the general public together with recommendations on how to use the public funds. It has no authority to impose any sanctions.

Against the decisions of the OPC, appeals can be submitted to the Regional Court in Brno and to the Supreme Administrative Court.

2.8 Denmark

The governance of education in Denmark is carried out by different central authorities on the basis of the level of education. There are four main bodies being responsible for the governance of education:

- the Ministry of Children, Gender Equality, Integration and Social Affairs is responsible for Early Childhood Education and Care
- the Ministry of Education is responsible for compulsory and post-compulsory education
- the Ministry of Higher Education and Science is responsible for higher education
- the Ministry of Culture is responsible for arts

There are other bodies appointed to help to shape national education policy:

- the National Agency for Quality and Supervision is a part of the Ministry of Education and is responsible for the administration of national and

international assessments and for providing quality support materials. It is also responsible for supervising public and private education providers.

- the School Council fulfils the advisory role and is entitled to commission official evaluations in primary and lower secondary public schools
- the Danish Evaluation Institute implements officially commissioned and independent evaluations
- other stakeholders: Local Government Denmark, private school organisations, Confederation of Danish employers, Danish Union of Teachers, associations of school leaders, students and parents

The Ministry of Education establishes goals and content, while the municipalities are responsible for the overall quality management of the school in their territory and for setting local objectives and conditions. Supervision of the schools is also the responsibility of the local municipalities. Generally, it can be stated that schools in Denmark have a high autonomy, meaning that the effective implementation of education policy is the responsibility of local governments, school leaders and teachers. These stakeholders have to implement nationally determined strategies at the school level. In every school, a school board is formed containing elected parents, teachers and student representatives. This school board implements education policies within the central and municipal framework. There is a difference regarding school boards in public and private schools, as in private schools the school board is elected by parents and has more responsibility to monitor school quality.

Post-compulsory education institutions are self-governing and have the right to develop educational opportunities and pedagogy. They still have to obey to the rules established by the Ministry of Education. Schools at lower secondary level make 44% of the decisions concerning their operation. 34% of the decisions are made by the local government, while 22% are made by the central or state government. In Denmark, the majority of expenditure on educational institutions is financed from public sources. The annual expenditure per student has been more than the OECD average, and teachers' salaries have been increased. In Denmark, funds are provided to both public and private schools depending on the number

of students. The aim is to reach similar funding to both types of schools taking into consideration that parents have to pay the fees for private schools, that means a considerable income for them. Most students attend public schools, and the municipalities are spending a larger share on education than in most OECD countries. The responsibility of municipalities includes the determination of the funding and the level of service provided to schools, as public schools are funded by local municipalities. In Denmark, there is a redistribution of taxes collected by the municipalities in order to decrease the differences between high income and low-income municipalities. The main goal of providing financial support from public money to private schools is to ensure and strengthen the opportunity to choose private education. In the case of upper secondary schools, funding by the central government is based on the number of students enrolled in the particular school. The number of grants also depends on student activity.

The public procurement system in Denmark is quite decentralized however there is considerable control built in the system.

The most important body in the procurement system is the Danish Competition and Consumer Authority that is responsible for the monitoring of the markets in terms of competition and it has got responsibilities in the operation of the public procurement system as well. The main functions of the Danish Competition and Consumer Authority are the followings:

- to support bidders understanding the legislation, rules and guidance
- to hear complaints in the early stage and if it is needed it brings these complaints in front of the Complaints Board. Decisions of the Complaints Board can be appealed to the ordinary courts.
- to perform reviews in term of compliance
- to report violations if any
- to operate the online portal for e-notification of public procurement

The central purchasing body is a publicly-owned company – SKI- that is owned by the Danish Ministry of Finance (55% of the shares) and the Association of Local Authorities of Denmark (45% of the shares). The aim behind the founding of SKI was

to improve the result of the public procurement processes through the aggregation of demand. It issues framework agreements that are open on a voluntary basis to all levels of government. It manages framework agreements regarding 15 product categories. The main clients of SKI are the municipalities.

The Modernisation Agency within the Ministry of Finance is responsible for laws, policy, monitoring and compliance regarding public procurements. It is another central purchasing body, but the procurement via the framework agreements of the Modernisation Agency is mandatory for all state agencies. For other public bodies, this kind of procurement is a possibility.

The main oversight body is the Court of Auditors that reports its findings to the Parliament regarding the efficiency, effectiveness of the purchase using public funds and the compliance with policy objectives. The work of the Court of Auditors is evaluated by external experts.

2.9 Estonia

In Estonia, the Ministry of Education and Research is responsible for the administration and development of education system in Estonia and for the funding of research and development activities at national level. Therefore the following activities are carried out by the Ministry:

- to ensure that education laws are observed
- to establish requirements for the national curriculum
- to establish rules for national supervision
- to allocate national funds for education
- to develop financial standards for local and school budgets
- to develop the national framework curriculum

There are other bodies appointed to help to shape the education policy of Estonia:

- The Estonian Quality Agency for Higher and Vocational Education carries out the accreditation of education institutions

- Foundation Innove coordinates activities regarding life-long learning development (mainly for general and vocational education). It organises training, national assessment, data collection, analysis and dissemination of education-related information.
- National Examination and Qualification Centre joined Foundation Innove in 2012
- The Archimedes Foundation implements different international and national programmes and projects in the field of training, education and research
- Municipalities play an important role in the education system: they organise the work of the pre-primary schools to deliver general education services and some parts of education for students with special needs. They also have the authority to hire school leaders and it is their responsibility to provide support for career counselling and psychological counselling in schools. They establish school supervisory bodies and implement county plans for educational development. Their activity also includes the support of lunch catering, medical services and hobby groups.
- The supervision of pre-primary and general education schools is done by the education departments of county governments. Other responsibilities of county governments are: formulating county-level plans for education development, disseminating information on public financing, organising cultural and educational events for teachers and students and giving advice to municipal governments on education issues.
- There are school supervisory bodies whose task is to discuss school development plans, to review school budget plans and curricula, to participate in teacher recruitment processes and school staff appointments, to approve salary rates for educational personnel proposed by the school leaders and to organise support for schools.

The administration of the schools is highly decentralised in Estonia, especially compared to the OECD average. Lower secondary schools make around 80% of the decisions related to themselves.

In most cases, the school management is carried out by the local governments, and they have to cover the running costs of the schools. Local governments have the following authorities regarding education institutions:

- to establish schools
- to re-arrange general education schools
- to close schools.

Besides the authority, local governments have some compulsory tasks in connection with general education:

- to keep account of the number of compulsory attending children
- to ensure school attendance control
- to make arrangements for school transport
- to provide school meals

Every municipal school gets a subsidy allocated from the state budget, that is calculated on the number of students. This subsidy is used for paying teachers' salaries, social taxes, training and textbooks. Private general education schools can also apply for a subsidy, but in this case, the state determines guidelines for the use of the allocated funds. These funds are calculated based on the number of students enrolled in the particular private school and living in the corresponding administrative territory.

Estonia is a very small country and the state has made investments above OECD average only at tertiary level in education. Despite that, the students in Estonia have performed great in PISA. The majority of the investments are covered by public sources.

The procurement system is centralized, while the central procurement policy belongs to the authority of Department of Public Procurement and State Aid (RRO) within the Ministry of Finance. The activities and responsibilities of the RRO include:

- to draft legislation and amendments to them
- to supervise public procurement processes
- to manage the e-procurement platform of Estonia

- to provide guidance and training to contracting authorities and also to potential suppliers

The public contracts are managed by the respective contracting authority, however on an ad hoc basis and voluntarily joint purchasing is also used.

Complaints against the procurement decisions can be sent to the Estonian Public Procurement Review Committee that operates as the review body of the first instance. The Committee is composed of three independent members who have got the right to invalidate contracts in case of serious irregularities. In case of an appeal, the Administrative Court is the first instance body. Appeals can be submitted to the Regional Courts and to the Court of Appeal, while the National Court of Estonia has the final decision.

Regarding public procurement processes, external controls are implemented by the National Audit Office (NAO). Internal auditors are authorized to conduct internal controls. The NAO performs audits of state agencies in terms of compliance and it also publishes annual reports and recommendations for the Parliament and the general public.

2.10 Finland

In Finland, the education system is very decentralised, and schools are allowed to make decisions individually. The preparation and implementation of the education policy is the obligation of the government and the Ministry of Education and Culture. Every four years the Education and Research Development Plan is prepared that includes the main priorities of the education policy. Other bodies taking part in the education system are:

- the National Board of Education outlines the national curricula for pre-primary, primary and secondary education
- evaluation is done by the education Evaluation Centre since 2014
- since 2013 the national curriculum of the early childhood education and care has been outlined by the Ministry of Education and Culture

- other bodies providing advice and expert services in connection with vocational education and training, lifelong learning, adult learning: National Education and Training Committees, National Coordination Group for Education and Training, Council for Lifelong Learning, Advisory Council for Youth Affairs, Advisory Board for Early Childhood Learning and Care
- other stakeholders are represented by unions, the relevant ones from the point of view of primary and secondary education are: students' unions, unions of education providers

In the decentralised education system in Finland, a considerable level of authorities belong to local level institutions (in general municipalities or joint municipal authorities). In the case of lower secondary schools, the decisions are made either by the local government or by the school at the local level. The form of how the decision making is organized in each municipality is the decisive factor which of the above-mentioned institutions have the authority to make decisions. In general, local authorities are responsible for the following tasks:

- to organise basic education
- to allocate the funding
- to determine the local curriculum
- to implement the local curriculum
- to employ, recruit and train teachers and other non-teaching staff

The extent of the autonomy of a school is determined by the local authority as well.

Pre-primary, primary, secondary, VET and even tertiary education is all financed from public funding sources. The majority of the basic upper secondary education institutions get funding from the central budget and local authorities. The government takes into consideration different factors when it decides how much funding goes to each municipality (from which education is financed):

- the proportion of the population (the main aim to balance it within the country)
- socio-economic status of the area

Private schools also receive public funding, however in general at all education levels less than 15% of the students choose a private education institution. The funding for pre-primary schools and basic education funding are included in statutory government transfers to basic municipal services, but the municipality has the right to make decisions about the allocation of the funding.

In Finland the public procurement system is quite decentralised, contracting authorities have the right to decide even whether they would like to conduct public procurement or not. Of course, this choice can only be made if the value of the purchase is below the European Union threshold.

At central level two ministries have the competencies regarding public procurement processes:

- The Ministry of Employment and Economy (MEE): it executes the national policymaking, drafts the national procurement legislation and its amendments, and provide help to economic actors and contracting authorities regarding the interpretation of the respective law.
- the Ministry of Finance is responsible for the management of central government procurement processes and it also determines the purchase strategy and conducts the centralised procurement.

The oversight body is the Finnish National Audit Office (NAO) which monitors and checks public procurement processes in terms of budget, accounting and financial operations. NAO reports the findings directly to the Parliament.

The Market Court act as a specific review body in the first instance having authority to cancel a decision of a contracting authority partly or even fully. Against its decisions appeals can be issued to the Supreme Administrative Court (SAC).

2.11 France

In France, the Ministry of National Education, Higher Education and Research is responsible for education. The Ministry determines and implements the policies regarding education, research, innovation and information and communication technologies (ICT). It also defines the national curriculum of France. The Ministry of

National Education, Higher Education and Research is organized on a regional basis. There are 13 academic regions that are responsible for maintaining national standards for education policy, along with 26 mainland academies and 4 academies in France's overseas territories responsible for public service aspects of education (this includes strategy definition and schools management).

In France there are three types of schools:

- State schools are run by the government.
- State-funded and controlled private schools have to issue an agreement with the government in the form of a contract. On the basis of the contract, the teachers' and other educational staff's salaries are covered by public funding. The funding of state schools and state-funded and controlled schools are the same.
- Privately funded schools are also inspected by the government regarding their management and teaching practices. That means that all the staff needs the required qualifications. The content of the teaching has to adopt the French education law and minimum standards of knowledge.

The education system of France is traditionally very centralised. On the local level, there are professionals appointed to ensure the implementation of national education policy. These professional players are Chief Education Officers, Academic Directors and school heads. As there has been a decentralisation process of the competencies in the administration of the educational system, local authorities are playing an increasingly significant role in the governance of education. They ensure the physical operation of the system through financing the construction and maintenance of school buildings, school transport and supply of educational materials, etc.).

Public procurement system is quite decentralized in France due to the semi-decentralized political structure and the size of the country. The system is characterized by the high number and wide range of contracting authorities and oversight institutions.

Public procurement methods cannot be standardized in France due to the distribution of authority and responsibility among the regional and local authorities. Another barrier is the relatively complex regulatory structure that means a high degree of discretion to contracting authorities together with a kind of burdensome feeling for potential suppliers to comply with. However, the number of public procurement procedures in France is among the highest in the European Union. The majority of these contracts are public works at regional and local levels.

The main institution regarding public procurements is the Ministry of Economy and Finance (Minefi) that has primary responsibility for the conditions governing the public procurement system. One of its departments, the Department of Legal Affairs (DAJ), is responsible for analysing regulations regarding public contracts and providing support and legal advice to State departments. The Department of Legal Affairs collects the data on procurement through the Public Procurement Economic Observatory (OEAP). The Ministry of Transport and the Ministry of Defence have developed practical tools in order to inform the contracting authorities on the development in their respective areas as these ministries make comparatively heavy use of public procurement.

France has a central purchasing body, called the "Union for Grouping Procurements (UGAP)" that is dedicated to the State, public organisations and local buyers. The State Purchasing Body (SAE) complements the tasks of the UGAP. The State Purchasing Body is responsible for awarding framework agreements and procurement contracts for common purchases of central administrations.

The Budget Ministry has got a Directorate General for Public Accounting (DGCP) that is appointed to give advice to local authorities on procurement. This is a considerable help as smaller local authorities do not have the necessary competence and expertise.

The National Court of Audits (CC) and its 27 inferior regional courts (CRC) are the main oversight bodies. The central comptrollers also take part in the oversight tasks. The comptrollers work at State level and they are internal overseers who are responsible to verify that public corporations, mixed enterprises, organisations and

businesses that have benefited from financial assistance, central agencies and national companies respect the principles of legality, economy and efficiency. The National Court of Audits and its regional courts provide external controls of public bodies' operating conditions and irregularities in these bodies' public procurement.

The Courts of Appeal is the last recourse instance, which decisions can be subject to review for compliance with the law by the State Council.

The Public Procurement Mediation is a government scheme created in order to facilitate economic operators' access to public procurement. It consists of national and regional bidder advocates who provide guidance on the navigation of the procurement process and it acts as impartial, neutral and independent conciliators in case of debates between contracting authorities and suppliers (especially small and medium-sized enterprises).

2.12 Germany

In Germany, the education system and its governance are semi-centralized, as the responsibility for it is shared between the Federal Government and the Federal States. Each Federal State has its own Ministry of Education and is responsible for schools, higher education, adult education and continuing education. The coordination between the different ministries of education is ensured by several bodies. The Federal Ministry of Education and Research manages nationwide policies for VET, tertiary education and foreign affairs within education. The coordination of education policies is the responsibility of the Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs of the Federal States that also gives recommendations for further developments regarding primary and secondary schools, higher education and research and cultural policy.

The following bodies also have a considerable role in the education system:

- the Joint Science Conference works with research funding, science and research policy strategies and science system

- the German Rectors' Conference is responsible for topics related to higher education
- the Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training is a federal government institution that is responsible for policy, research and practice in VET
- other ministries such as the Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs work on topics related to the labour market and equity issues
- stakeholders such as teachers under the umbrella of their union's influence policy making

In Germany, most of the decisions regarding primary and secondary education are made at the level of Federal States. They are responsible for the organisation, planning, management and supervision of the school's mission, personnel recruitment and remuneration of teachers. Local authorities are responsible for the construction and maintenance of school buildings.

In Germany (as in most of the countries) the public sources dominate the financial cover of the investments on education. In the different Federal States, there are considerable differences between the expenditure due to the individual education systems of them covering the remuneration, teaching hours and demographic trends. Regarding the public schools funding responsibility is split between the Federal States (e.g. remuneration of teachers and recruitment) and the local authorities (e.g. material costs and remuneration of non-teaching staff). In the case of a few Federal State support through lump sum allocations are given to the local authorities. These allocations are basically used for the (re)construction of schools.

In Germany the public procurement system focuses on economic efficiency and recently environmental and social sustainability has become part of the objectives. Due to the political system of the country, the public procurement system is highly decentralized. The main central authority that is in charge of the public procurement system is the Federal Ministry of Economy and Energy (BMWi), whose tasks are to decide on the principles of public procurement and to draft primary

legislation. The Federal States Committee on public procurement ensures regular cooperation with the Federal States in order to share the latest aspects of the procurement policy and practice.

There are Public Procurement Committees serving as a forum for stakeholders from the federal level, federal state level and local administration level, as well as for public-private organisations and private entities. The Committees participate in drafting procurement rules. The procurement rules are the responsibilities of two other organisations as well divided on the basis of the type of procurement:

- The German Committee for Supplies and Services Tendering and Contract Regulations (DVAL) participates in the development of procurement rules for supplies and services
- the German Committee for Construction Tendering and Contract Regulations (DVA) works on the procurement rules for public works

At the federal level Germany has four central contracting authorities between which the responsibilities are shared based on the thematic content:

- the Federal Financial Directorate Southwest (BFD Südwest) implements procurements for the tax administration
- the Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing issues framework agreements for groups of specific technical products
- the Federal Office for Equipment, IT technology and Use of the German Armed Forces procures mainly for the German military
- the Central Purchasing Body of the Ministry of Interior is the main body among the central purchasing/contracting bodies, as it procures for all federal agencies and manages the main e-procurement platform including the provision of the supportive functions

There are central purchasing bodies on a regional level as well.

The oversight system of public procurement processes is linked to the EU threshold: Above the thresholds, the procurements are controlled by procurement review chambers that are in charge of the first instance reviews. Each federal State has its

own procurement review chamber, and there is a central review organisation within the Federal Competition Authority (Federal Procurement Review Chamber). Appeals against the decisions of the review chambers can be submitted to the specialised procurement senates in the respective Higher Regional Courts. In case of procurements below the EU thresholds, most of the federal states have founded review bodies called VOB or VOL Offices. The supervision of the public procurement procedures is carried out by the Audit Courts of the German Federal States and by the Federal Court of Auditors in terms of cost-effectiveness and compliance.

2.13 Greece

In Greece, the education system is fairly centralised as the essential competencies regarding education policy and administration are the responsibility of the Ministry of Education, research and Religious Affairs.

Other bodies that play an important role in education are:

- Committee on Cultural and Educational Affairs
- Dialogue Committee
- National Council for Education (EYSP)
- Institute of Educational policy (IEP)

The National Council for Education is a central advisory board to the Minister of Education, Research and Religious Affairs for topics regarding education planning and major issues of educational policy.

The Institute of Educational Policy is a private law entity operating under the supervision of the Ministry of Education, research and Religious Affairs. It is appointed to provide scientific support to the Ministry acting in the public interest.

The main focus points are the following:

- scientific research and analysis at the primary and secondary education level
- the transition from secondary to higher education
- constant technical support in the planning and implementation of educational policies

The Institute of Educational Policy operates within the framework provided by the National and Social Dialogue for Education as an educational consultant for all three bodies that are included in the Dialogue: Dialogue Committee, Committee on Cultural and Educational Affairs and the National Council for Education.

The management and governance at different levels are developed by the following bodies:

- at central level: the Ministry of Education, research and Religious Affairs
- at the regional level: the Regional Directorates of Education
- at the local level: the Primary Directorates of Education and the Secondary Directorates of Education and School Units

The bodies listed above have different responsibilities and tasks. The Minister of Education, research and Religious Affairs determines the long-term objectives and functioning of the education system supported by collective, consultative and advisory bodies. The definition of the curricula content, the writing and distribution of the textbooks, the allocation of teaching time, teacher education and initial training, the placement of teachers and other staff, teacher salaries and school financing are the particular tasks of the Ministry.

The Regional Education Directorates implement administrative controls, referring directly to the Minister of Education, Research and Religious Affairs. It includes the administration, scientific and pedagogical guidance of education in their own region. Therefore the Directorates are responsible for supervising the implementation of the national education policy, tailoring it to the specific requirements of the region, and connecting the regional education services with the central education authorities. Each Directorate consists of different parts: the Department of Administration and the Department of Scientific, and Pedagogical Guidance.

There is a subordinated situation between the two bodies acting on a local level, as the School Units fall under the relevant Directorate of Education (Primary or

Secondary Directorate) and the Directorates of Primary and Secondary Education fall within the competence of the Regional Directorate of Education. Schools have gained more and more authority including the ability to plan, organise and evaluate their own work.

The public procurement legal system is uniquely complex in Greece with 400 laws, regulations and presidential decrees. This complex system is the reason for the lack of uniformity throughout the laws and regulations creating different concepts and definitions that are also not identical with those in the EU Directives.

One of the concepts and definitions that does not have a unique classification is the awarding authority. The awarding authorities have the right to use open, restricted or negotiated procedures with or without publication for notice in case that the purchase is below the EU threshold. In case of the procurement of goods, services and work contracts below 60 000 EUR, awarding authorities have the right to choose to use simplified bidding procedures under certain conditions. The permission for direct award happens in the following cases:

- below 20 000 EUR in case of State authorities
- below 15 000 EUR in case of local and regional authorities.

The primary procurement organization is the Hellenic Single Procurement Authority (SPPA) that is responsible for the following tasks:

- managing central government procurements of works, supplies and services
- for providing policy advice to the legislature
- for providing guidance to awarding authorities on the application of procurement law and regulation
- for authorising the use of special procedures (e.g. negotiated procedure without publication notice)
- playing a supervisory role through monitoring and evaluating awarding authorities' decisions for effectiveness and implementing random checks of on-going processes for compliance with the law.

For public works procurement and public services contract for public works the General Secretariat for Public Works (GSPW) in the Ministry of Economy, Development and Tourism is responsible.

Within the organisation of the Ministry of Economy, Development and Tourism, the General Secretariat of Commerce (GSC) is the owner and coordinator of the e-procurement system in Greece and is responsible for public supplies and services. Furthermore, the Ministry of Interior and Administrative Reconstruction has some power in jurisdiction over procurement as it is focused on public organisation and administration matters including the relationship between the State and society. It also coordinates policies regarding the e-governance and administrative reforms. The Administrative Authority of Public Contracts is responsible for the supervision, control and implementation of tendering processes and conclusions of public contracts, and it controls and ensures the compliance with the Greek and European legislation.

If a contract exceeds the value of 1 000 000 EUR, the contracting authority has to submit all relevant documents to the Court of Auditors which will check the legality and efficiency of the contract. On the local level there are Government Representatives (Secretary Generals of the Region) appointed to examine the decisions made by the local authorities during the awarding process. In case of any irregularity regarding the execution process of a contract, the Body of Inspectors of Public Procurement Works will control the respective contracting authorities.

The procurement process is slightly different in municipalities than in other contracting authorities as every municipality has a dedicated Department of Finance and also a Procurement Office. On the basis of the "Procurement Regulation of Local Authorities", they are responsible for the implementation and coordination of the public procurement processes in municipalities.

2.14 Hungary

In Hungary, the education system is semi-centralised as the responsibilities are shared between the central government and municipal school districts. At the central level, the Ministry of Human capacities (EMMI) is responsible for primary schools, secondary schools and tertiary education. EMMI develops the national curriculum, develops and selects the textbooks, defines the teachers' salaries together with the teachers' career system, and the budget for primary and secondary education. Previously the VET system was under the authority of the Ministry of National Economy, but in July 2018 the Hungarian government decided to introduce a new ministry of which one of the main priorities and tasks will be the responsibility for Vocational Education and Training and adult training.

There are other bodies appointed to participate in the governance of the Hungarian education system:

- the Educational Authority (OH) carries out international and national student assessments, performs legal and professional control and educational evaluation, audits. It is also responsible for developing criteria for the assessment and qualification exams of teachers. The Educational Authority also manages databases for schools.
- the National Public Education Council is the professional advisory body of the Ministry of Human Capacities through making proposals for decision-making
- their advisory body: the Hungarian Institute for Research and Development
- the National Vocational and Adult Training Office is also an advisory body working for the Ministry of National Economy at the moment
- the Klebelsberg Centre is the main body and it helps the procurements and decision making of all municipal school districts which belong to them

Municipalities are responsible for delivering early childhood education and care. The autonomy of the municipal school's districts has been increased in recent years, which means that at the moment these districts can decide on low-value procurements.

Since 2013 public school funding is managed directly by the Klebelsberg Centre which allocates funds from the budget of the Ministry of Human Capacities. The salaries of teachers, the transportation costs, and costs of construction, renovation and extensions are financed by the Klebelsberg Centre. For the definition of the number of funds, student numbers and socio-economic circumstances are taken into consideration. Independent private schools also receive funding for their operation, but these funds are allocated directly by the Ministry of Human Capacities.

In Hungary, two main bodies are responsible for the public procurement system: the Prime Minister's Office (PMO) and the Public Procurement Authority (KH). The responsibilities are shared in the following system:

- the Prime Minister's Office drafts legislation related to public procurement and provides support and guidance to contracting authorities. It acts as an internal oversight body through performing controls of public procurement procedures in terms of compliance with regulations
- the Public Procurement Authority is the primary executive agency. It is responsible for monitoring the compliance with the law and developing opinions on draft legislation. It also collects and publishes information via annual reports, the Public Procurement Bulletin and the central register of award procedures. The Public Procurement Authority provides support to contracting authorities in terms of implementation-related questions and issues non-binding guidance documents, organizes training and seminars for practitioners.

The Directorate General for Public Procurement and Supply (KEF) is the central purchasing body for central government agencies. The use of the KEF is obligatory, especially in the case of some product categories, such as software and IT services, vehicles and office products.

At the local level, contracting authorities have the right and they are obliged to implement their own public procurement processes, however, it is allowed by law to use the central purchasing body in their territories.

The State Audit Office (SAO) performs external overviews of public procurement procedures. The SAO's recommendations are mandatory for contracts in case of serious irregularities.

As a first step, claims can be submitted to the contracting authorities, but if it is not solved in a way that is acceptable for both parties, it can be forwarded to the Public Procurement Arbitration Board (KDB), which has the authority to impose fines and sanctions and it can also exclude tenderers from participating in future procurement. Appeals against the decision of the KDB can be sent to the regional courts, and the decisions of the regional courts are subject to review by the Curia (Supreme Court of Hungary).

2.15 Ireland

In Ireland the administration of education is centralised. Under the direction of the Minister for Education and Skills the Department of Education and Skills (DES) is appointed for the administration. It is responsible for the following tasks:

- setting the general regulations for the recognition of schools
- approving the curriculum developed by the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment
- establishing regulations for management, resourcing and staffing of schools
- negotiating teachers' salary scales and conditions
- determining the conditions governing qualifications of teachers on the advice of the Teaching Council of Ireland
- approving staff numbers in schools and education and training boards
- determining the frameworks regarding the budget and the staff for Further and Higher Education and Training

The day-to-day work of the Department is implemented by the administrative staff under the direction of the Secretary-General. The main functions of the Department of Education and Skills are the following:

- giving advice to the Minister regarding the analysis of available data and extensive engagement with stakeholders based on the policy

- cooperating with stakeholders through their national representative bodies, such as parents' councils, school management bodies, teacher unions, employers and social partners, community organisations, institutional associations, special education organisations, other Government Departments, European Union, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
- Coordinating and implementing the policy approved by the Minister
- Confirming the curriculum developed by the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment in early learning, primary and post-primary contexts
- Acknowledging and funding the schools, Higher Education Authority and other education organisations through paying the salaries of the teachers and the other staff. The payment is not the responsibility of the Department if a coordinating intermediate exists.
- Discussing the educational staff's pay and conditions
- providing services for children with special educational needs with the help of the National Council for Special Education
- Assuring the quality and ensuring the professional development in the field of education
- Gathering data and participating in research
- Maintaining international relations and supporting the internationalisation of education

There are agencies working under the direction of the Department of Education and Skills. These agencies are appointed to carry out different tasks. From them the tasks of the six most important agencies are described below:

1. National Council for Curriculum and Assessment: advising on and developing the curriculum for primary and secondary schools, and for early childhood education

2. National Council for Special Education: advising on and policy and education services for persons with special educational needs focusing on children
3. State Examinations Commission: controlling the Junior Certificate at the end of the lower-secondary school and the Leaving Certificate at the end of the upper secondary education
4. SOLAS: being responsible for policy, coordination and funding of programmes of Further Education and Training
5. Higher Education Authority
6. Quality and Qualifications in Ireland: maintaining the national framework of qualifications in the educational and training sector, providing external quality assurance tasks for further and higher education and training, coordinating the international education

The Department of Education and Skills has 9 regional offices in Ireland, however education, in general,, is not organised on a regional basis. Higher education organisations formed regional clusters in order to meet the regional needs but in primary and secondary level this regional integration and collaboration are missing. The majority of post-primary schools and all the primary schools are owned and managed by local organisations and on these levels, there is a lack of regional or local structure. Each school is managed by a management board representatives of parents, teachers, local community and trustees. The schools have to obey the policy, funding, curriculum and staffing framework approved by the Department of Education and Skills. In Ireland, local authorities have got responsibility for example community issues but their remit does not include education.

The public procurement system of Ireland is quite modern and high performing, and many services are offered online nationally. The system underwent a transformation into a more centralised and more standardised public procurement system. However, tendering responsibilities still belong to the individual contracting authorities (at the state level and local level). After the economic crisis, the

government made efforts to incorporate environmental goals, energy efficiency goals and the encouragement of the use of sustainable materials into the system. Economic policy goals were also incorporated such as the promotion of innovation and addressing long-term unemployment.

The most important organisation in the public procurement system in Ireland is the Office of Government Procurement (OGP) under the direction of the Ministry for Public Expenditure and Reform (MPER). Its tasks and main responsibilities are the following:

- forming the public procurement policy
- disseminating the best practices
- providing general guidance regarding the processes
- managing the e-procurement strategy of the government

The Office of Government Procurement now fulfils the key executive role regarding acting as the central purchasing body and oversight body. Therefore, the OGP has set new goals:

- to standardise the procurement process in Ireland
- to achieve savings by implementing a systematic approach to public procurement

The Office of Government Procurement also manages the e-procurement platform and e-Tenders. The oversight responsibilities belong to different boards and the management of individual contracting authorities together with the Office of the Comptroller and Auditor General implementing external checks of procurement in order to ensure compliance with the procurement regulation.

Another important body in the Procurement System is the Irish High Court being responsible for first instance review processes. The last recourse instance is the Supreme Court. A complete public procurement process can last up to 3 years however it can be shortened to 6-12 months in some cases such as if the

participating organisations ask for transferring the case to the commercial division of the High Court.

2.16 Italy

In Italy the responsibility for education is shared between the main authority at the central level – the Ministry of Education, University and Research (MIUR) - and the regions. The Ministry is responsible for setting general guidelines, minimum standards of education and fundamental principles. MIUR is also responsible to ensure the quality of the education system, the allocation of financial resources from the state budget, and the maintenance and improvement of the cooperation between education and cultural institutions and organisations. The responsibility of the regions includes the legislative authority of vocational training.

There are other bodies that are the main actors in the education system:

- the Higher Council for Education creates proposals and shares its opinion regarding school staff, the assessment system of the education and the general organisation of education and the general objectives
- the National Institute for the Educational Evaluation of Instruction and Training (INVALSI) is responsible for the management of the overall evaluation of the Italian education system
- the National Institute for Documentation, Innovation and Educational research (INDIRE) is the main organisation belonging to the Ministry of Education, University and Research in connection with education research and innovation
- the National Institute for Public Policy Analysis (INAPP) is a new public research body being controlled by the Ministry of Labour and Social Policy. This institute is responsible for research regarding the connection and effects of different policies and the labour market
- the National University Council (CUN) and the National Council for Higher Education in Art and Music (CNAM) take part in the planning and approval of university regulations

- the National Agency for the Evaluation of the University and Research System (ANVUR) is the main assessment body of higher education institutions
- the Conference of Rectors and Italian Universities (CRUI) helps the Ministry of Education, University and Research in setting general higher education objectives and in the allocation of financial resources

The regional system of Italy includes 20 regions that have main responsibilities regarding education. The State-Regions Conference is the organisation through which regions cooperate with the state. Regions have to provide school premises and the conditions to ensure the right to study (e.g. textbooks, transportation). Regions are also responsible for organising the school network. Municipalities have responsibility for similar services provided for pre-schools and primary schools.

The autonomy of schools from pre-primary to secondary level is higher than the OECD average, as they have several rights regarding the general objectives and standards set by the Ministry of Education, University and Research. Their rights also include the allocation of resources and autonomy over the curriculum and assessment. Their autonomy over assessment means that they establish the student assessment policies and they choose which textbooks to use. In the decision-making process, the main bodies that are responsible for the particular decisions are the state and the schools. In the organisations of the schools, the main roles are the school manager, the director of general and administrative services, and several boards and committees through which students and parents are also represented in the Italian education system.

In the funding system, the proportion of education investments as a share of the GDP is lower than the OECD average, however, the majority of the resources are from the state budget. Some subnational governments also contribute to the expenditures. Italian public schools are directly funded by the Ministry of Education, University and Research in case of various criteria, such as enough available human resources and the existence of the student body. Schools have got autonomy regarding the financial resources as they can decide on which to

spend these sources earmarked to specific purposes. As mentioned above, regions and municipalities provide the funding for school transport, textbooks, social and health assistance, school canteens. They also provide financial aid for schools and provide funding for school building maintenance.

The responsibility for the Italian public procurement system is shared between two bodies:

- The Department of European Union Policies is responsible for the relation of the Italian government with European Union institutions, it coordinates the public procurement policies at the national, regional and local level
- The Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport is mainly responsible for proposing draft legislation and providing help for contracting authorities mainly in terms of the proper implementation of EU regulations

The Department of Development and Economic Cohesion is in charge of the management and assessment of national investments carried out through the use of EU Structural Funds. The main central purchasing body is Consip, which is a publicly owned stock company. The aim of the foundation of Consip was to implement the so-called Programme for Rationalisation of Public Expenditure and to strengthen the role of e-procurement. The main oversight body is the National Anti-Corruption Authority (ANAC) that implements controls in terms of compliance with rules and regulations and collects data on procurement through the Public Procurement Observatory. Italy's Court of Audit is also an oversight body, but it is not allowed for it to conduct any checks without prior warning.

2.17 Latvia

In Latvia, the education system is highly decentralized as it involves a wide range of institutions from national and municipal level. At the national level there are three main education policy institutions:

- the Ministry of Education and Science (MoES)
- the Parliament (as the main legislative body)

- the Cabinet of Ministers (as the main executive body)

The Ministry of Education and Science is responsible for the policy development, its implementation and supervision and the setting of educational standards at primary and secondary levels. The work of the Ministry of Education and Science is supported by many subordinated agencies that are involved in the supervision of the Latvian education system:

- the National Centre for Education has several tasks:
 - to develop the curricula and examinations for pre-primary, basic and general secondary education, vocational education
 - to develop the subject standards and sample teaching-learning programmes
 - to provide professional qualification development for teachers
 - to provide educational opportunities to children with special needs
 - to provide interest-related education which is very important in the schools in Latvia
- the State Education Quality Service is appointed for the supervision of education quality and to inspect the education system from primary to upper secondary and tertiary level for all the public and private schools. It is also responsible for registering the education institutions, licensing education programmes and carrying out school (re)accreditation
- the Latvian Language Agency implements the state language policy
- the State Education Development Agency has to implement the national education policy and to control activities related to EU programmes and other international cooperations
- the Agency for International Programmes for Youth has very diverse activities from which one of the most important regarding the topic of this report is that this agency supports links between non-formal learning and lifelong education
- the Latvian Council of Science and the Latvian Academy of Sciences have activities and responsibilities in relation with research and development

In Latvia, the municipalities are responsible for providing primary, secondary and informal education while cooperating with the Ministry of Education and Science through the Education Boards of Municipalities. These Boards allocate the state budget for the salaries of teachers and other pedagogical staff, provide materials for teaching and ensure that there are opportunities for teachers to improve their qualification.

In Latvia, the education programmes have to be developed according to the General education Law, but each school has the right to form its own programme. These programmes have to meet the centrally determined education standards as well. Schools can also hire their own staff. In the case of most of the public vocational schools and special schools, the government is the responsibility of the Ministry of education and Science. The same rules apply to private schools in terms of registration, licensing and accreditation.

The funding of primary and secondary schools is done by the central government and municipalities. While the salaries of teachers are provided directly from the state budget, municipalities have to cover the costs for the maintenance of school buildings. The funding and supervision of vocational schools are split between the Ministry of Education and Science, the Ministry of Culture, the Ministry of Interior Affairs, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Welfare, municipalities and the private sector. The funding of primary and upper secondary schools are provided on the basis of the number of students enrolled. The school leader is responsible and has the autonomy regarding the use of financial and material resources and the salaries of employees. In the case of private schools, funding is the responsibility of the founders unless the school fulfils compulsory education purposes when the state also allocates funding.

Public procurement system in Latvia is decentralized, central and local contracting authorities manage their own public procurement processes. In terms of procurement policy and legislation, the responsibility belongs to the Ministry of Finance (MoF). For the monitoring function, the Procurement Monitoring Bureau (IUB) is appointed that is supervised by the Ministry of Finance. IUB is responsible for

the preparation of guidelines and instructions, and drafts of standardised tender and contract documents. The IUB prepares annual reports to the government of Latvia on the basis of its findings and results regarding the monitoring and functioning of the public procurement system. IUB also fulfils reviewer functions acting as the first instance for complaints. In cases of projects co-financed by ESI funds, the Procurement Monitoring Bureau is entitled to implement ex-ante monitoring before the beginning of the public procurement procedure.

The State Regional Development Agency (VRAA) manages the e-procurement system and framework agreements for certain types of products and services. According to the framework agreements e-catalogues are made, the use of which is mandatory for central government institutions in case of a purchase. The main external oversight body is the State Audit Office (SAO) which is an independent collegial supreme audit institution. It reviews public procurement procedures in terms of the effective, legally correct use of central and local resources. The SAO also creates recommendations in order to reduce the deficiencies. The SAO reports its findings to the IUB, that has the right to impose sanctions in case of any irregularities.

The Corruption Prevention and Combating Bureau (KNAB) plays a supporting role in the public procurement system through detecting corruption in the procedures cooperating with the IUB. Complaints regarding public procurement procedure can be issued to the administrative court which has the right to annul, terminate and even amend or reduce the contractual terms of a tender process.

2.18 Lithuania

In the education system of Lithuania, the Ministry of Education and Science is the main authority with responsibilities of formulating and executing the national education and science policies. The Ministry is also in charge of outlining strategic education plans, annual programmes and of submitting proposals to the Government. Its tasks include the organisation of matura examinations, approval of the general content of teaching, training and studies according to the

framework of formal education (it includes general programmes, subject-specific programmes and teaching – training – study plans). The Ministry is also responsible for issues such as national standards for accomplished education levels (the exceptions are higher education and PhD studies), standards for vocational training, guidelines for higher educational studies, accreditation criteria according to curricula and order of accreditation.

The implementation of the national education policy is the responsibility of the County Manager's Administration. Other tasks of this organisation are to approve strategic education plans for the county, to supervise the activities of subordinate education providers, as well as to form special school network and to assure the teaching of students with special needs according to programmes of compulsory and general education.

Municipalities have got a considerable role in the execution of the national education policy in the area of the municipality. It includes the approval of the strategic education plans for the municipality and the general plan for the restructuring of the school network and forming of the pre-primary, primary, and basic and secondary school networks. It is also responsible for the ensuring of the necessary environment for the provision of compulsory education. Municipalities also intend to form a network of vocational training and adult education providers in a way that this network is built on the basis of the needs of the population. Forming a network of non-formal education providers is also a subject of the municipalities' responsibility.

Other important actors in the education system in Lithuania are the school founders. Each school founder is obliged to ensure the execution of the national education policy and relevant laws, other legislation regarding school activities. They are responsible for the execution of the respective school. Usually, the municipalities are the school founders in the case of public schools in the field of general education, however, in the case of private schools, private entities play the role of the school founder. The Ministry of Education and Science is the founder of vocational schools and schools of general education accepting students from

all over the country. The Government of the Republic of Lithuania (in case of state-funded colleges) and the Seimas of the Republic of Lithuania (in the case of state universities) are also school founders.

The majority of the expenditure in the education system is financed from the central budget and also by the municipalities. The funding mechanism depends on the type of the school, such as:

- state-funded schools
- municipal schools
- non-state-funded schools

The above mentioned financial resources are not available for higher education institutions and for programmes of non-formal education.

A financial mechanism involving state budget and municipal resources means that the financing mechanism is implemented through the student's basket that is allocated on the basis of the number of the students enrolled. The student's basket covers the salaries of teachers, the cost of textbooks, and the cost of different teaching materials and in-service training of teachers. The founders of the schools also finance the maintenance costs of the schools through allocation the necessary resources.

There are non-state funded schools belonging to religious communities or associations implementing formal educational programmes are financed from allocations from the budget for teaching funds and school maintenance. This financing is implemented in proportion to the state-funded and municipal schools of the same type, and this financial mechanism is possible if there is a respective international agreement.

The funding of vocational schools, post-secondary schools and schools of non-formal education are financed by their founder. State-funded higher education institutions get every year allocated money from the state budget.

In Lithuania, public procurement processes are carried out by subnational contracting authorities with a strong control and reporting system of the national procurement supervising body.

The procurement policy is set by the Ministry of Economy and the implementation of the policy is the responsibility of three main national bodies: Public Procurement Office (PPO), Competition Council and Central Purchasing Organisation (CPO). These bodies have different tasks as follows:

- Public Procurement Office implements the public procurement policy and also ensures the compliance with the law and legislation rules. It also has to provide methodological help to contracting authorities, to administer the central e-procurement portal, to prevent irregularities, to ensure the compliance of contracting authorities with the law and to coordinate and monitor public procurement processes
- Competition Council inquires possible anti-competitive practices both from the sides of contracting authorities and of bidders. The Council reports its finding to the PPO, and can issue fines
- Central Purchasing Organisation is responsible for centralised procurement procedures on behalf of contracting authorities such as central administration and its territorial branches, local authorities. It makes sure that the respective framework agreements are issued for a wide range of products, services and public works, from which later the contracting authorities can choose using an e-catalogue.

Another important organisation in the public procurement system in the Republic of Lithuania is the National Audit Office (NAO) being the supreme audit institution. Its main aim is to ensure the efficient management of the State property. It implements its activities according to the Public Audit Strategy and the annual audit programmes. The National Audit office conducts performance and financial audits reports audit findings and also coordinates regularly its activities with the Public Procurement Office.

2.19 Luxembourg

In Luxembourg, the education system is being developed towards a more decentralised system. At the state level, the Ministry of National Education,

Childhood and Youth is in charge of public education, vocational education and training. It has got several tasks including:

- planning and administering all teaching in public schools
- managing the curriculum and diplomas
- managing the access to public schools
- appointing staff

The Ministry of Higher Education and Research sets the framework for higher education.

There are other institutions, authorities that help to shape the education system:

- the Higher Council for National Education plays the role of the advisor of the Ministry of National Education, Childhood and Youth (MENJE) through providing recommendations regarding educational reforms, teaching and learning
- The National School Commission is an organization of representatives of mayors, teachers, parents, district administrators, teachers' unions and MENJE, and its task is to develop proposals for reforms, research and teacher training
- the National Commissions for Programmes includes the commissions for every subject taught in secondary schools. In the commissions, every secondary school is represented. These commissions are responsible for proposing the school curriculum and teaching materials regarding each subject
- SCRIPT operates under the control of the Ministry of National Education, Childhood and Youth implementing pedagogical and technological innovation and research. It also ensures the quality of education in schools and colleges and providing continuous training for teachers and other educational staff
- the College for Inspectors and the College of Directors regularly hold meetings for discussing reforms and national policies
- the National Institute for the Development of Continuous Vocational Training (INFPC) operates under the control of the Ministry of National Education, Childhood and Youth aiming to promote the training by

developing different information tools and working directly with the social partners of the VET sector

In Luxembourg, public schools do not have as much autonomy as in other countries in the OECD in general. Fundamental schools belong to one of the 21 local authorities and each of these authorities is led by an inspector. The schools are managed jointly by the state and the municipalities. Public secondary schools, however, are managed directly by the Ministry of National Education, Childhood and Youth appointing the school leaders and setting the legal and financial frameworks for each school.

The funding system and the source of funding depending on the type of each school. Fundamental public schools are funded directly by the Ministry of National Education, Childhood and Youth and by local education authorities. The Ministry pays for the staff costs on the basis of the allocated teaching lessons and taking into account socio-economic indicators. Local authorities provide financial sources for services beyond this quota and for infrastructure, school equipment. The state funds directly the secondary schools and they have got the autonomy to manage their financial resources. The allocation of the funds is based on the budget plan created by the school leader. The allocation has to be approved by the school's Education Council. The costs of the buildings and teachers in technical secondary schools are covered by the MENJE similar to the costs related to school education and initial VET. Private schools can also apply for state subsidies the amount of which depend on whether the school follows the national curriculum.

Public procurement system reflects the characteristics of the country as all the public procurement processes are organized through one major platform. The responsible policy body is the Public Procurement Directorate within the Public Works Department of the Ministry of Sustainable Development and Infrastructure (MDDI). The Directorate is in charge of the regulatory framework, legislation development, monitoring and implementation.

Within the MDDI a consultative body also works – the Tender Commission – which is composed of representatives from the contracting authorities, cottage industries

and chamber of commerce. It overviews the processes in order to ensure the compliance with the regulations, and its findings are generally adopted by the contracting authorities hence they are not binding. It also processes the complaints regarding public procurement processes and decisions. Tenderers are allowed to submit their complaints directly to the contracting authority and in this case, this complaint does not have any effect on the procedure. Appeals should be submitted to the administrative court or to civil and commercial courts.

The two main appointed supervision bodies are the National Court of Auditors – that investigates a set of public organisations on a yearly basis, however, no official report is created from the findings- and the Competition Council – that regularly issues decisions on unfair competition in public procurement procedures.

2.20 Malta

In the education system, the most important authority that forms the education policy is the Ministry of Education and Employment (MEDE). The MEDE is responsible for all publicly funded schools in Malta. As due to the size of the country in Malta there is no regional level and the management and governance of education take place at central and local levels. The Ministry of education and Employment have the following tasks and responsibilities regarding the education system:

- to prepare educational legislation
- to make decisions e.g. about their share within the state budget

There are appointed bodies to help the MEDE with the administration of education system:

- Permanent Secretary is the top civil servant in the Ministry of Education and Employment assisted by the following three Directors General (DGs) administering the three respective Directorates of Education
 - Directorate for Quality and Standards in education (DQSE) is responsible for setting and monitoring standards and it ensures the quality of teaching both in state and non-state schools
 - Directorate for Educational Services (DES) provides the physical infrastructure and also the resources and it also provides support services to colleges, educational staff, parents and students

- o Directorate for Corporate Services (DCS) is responsible for the provision of central support service and the coordination of the corporate activities of the departments falling under the MEDE. It also provides support to these departments on issues regarding financial planning and management, human resource management, procurement and office management. Its tasks include the harmonization and creation of the Ministry of Education and Employment's business plans, financial forecasts and annual reports.

In Malta, each public school has a school council including teachers, parents and students (if they are at least 16 years old). The members of these school councils are selected by regular elections every two years. The school councils play a consultative role to the senior management team of each school.

Since the last major reform in the administrative system of education, all state schools on Malta now part of the Colleges. Each College has its own legal personality. Each College Principal can take decisions concerning schools within the College. The College principal fulfils the chair role in the Council of Heads for the schools within the respective college. The most important role of the Council of Heads is to ensure the creation of the common identity. On the basis of the Education Act, every town and village should have its own primary school. Now the majority of the primary schools have their kindergarten attached to them. The primary schools send their student to the secondary school in the same College.

Malta has got a centralised government system, as well as public procurement system. Thus there is one central departmental agency being responsible for all national level procurement procedures, and this agency also acts as the only central purchasing body. Still, the majority of the public procurement contracts are handled by individual central and also local government contracting authorities.

The Department of Contracts (DoC) within the Ministry of Finance is the central public procurement body in Malta. The following tasks belong to it:

- to outline public procurement legislation and policy
- to prepare guidelines and instructions

- to collect statistical data
- to create annual monitoring reports about the functioning of the public procurement system
- to provide legal advice to contracting authorities together with the Attorney General

The Department of Contracts – as mentioned above- also acts as the only central purchasing body in Malta. It should act as the purchasing body for contracts which value exceeds 120 000 EUR. Local councils have the authority to administer their own public procurement processes. Contracts with a value between 6 000 EUR and 120 000 EUR are procured through departmental calls for tender with only a limited contribution from the Department of Contracts.

The Department of Contracts has the right to establish ad-hoc committees for the role of monitoring the procedures regarding contracts exceeding 120 000 EUR. Within the Department, the General Contracts Committee provides support through information collecting and investigation of claims of irregularities as well as making recommendations on tender decisions both to the Department and local contracting authorities.

There are two appointed main supervisory bodies with the below-mentioned functions:

- the National Audit Office (NAO) issues independent supervision on public organisation including their public procurement procedures. It also creates a thematic analysis of the effectiveness of the public procurement system regularly including procedures carried out in the framework of EU-funded projects. The Public Accounts Committee is the most important entity within the NAO whose responsibility is to assess and examine the financial administration of the public sector. Its tasks also include the promotion of improvements if they are needed and to encourage the economic, efficient and effective use of the public sources.

- the Internal Audit and Investigation Department (IAID) carries out audits on different areas of government policies. The report created by IAID is not publicly available.

Another important body in the public procurement system of Malta is the Public Contracts Review Board is responsible for receiving complaints from bidders taking part in tenders exceeding 10 000 EUR of value. Appeals against the decision of the Review Board can be made to the Court of Appeal.

2.21 Netherlands

In the Netherlands the education system is highly centralized, however, schools have a high level of autonomy. For the quality of the education system, the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science (OCW) is responsible. Its task is to set the education policy for early childhood education and care, primary and secondary education including education standards, examinations and funding mechanism. For tertiary education, the Ministry determines the teaching and examination framework. There are other bodies that contribute to shaping the education policy:

- the Education Inspectorate monitors the quality in educational institutions, while the Statistics Netherlands (Central Bureau of Statistics) collects and analyses data on education
- the Dutch Education Council includes leading academics, administrators and other experts on education being an independent advisory body
- Ministries responsible for the main areas of the country address specific education issues
- there are many stakeholder organisations: unions of teachers, unions of school leaders, umbrella organisations of school boards and the Education Co-operative which includes the five leading teachers' organisations and supports the quality of the teaching profession
- other professional institutes and research institutes also take part in forming the education policy, e.g. the National General Institute for Curriculum Development, the Central Institute for Test Development, the Netherlands' School Leaders Academy, school support agencies, etc.

Municipalities have responsibilities regarding particular areas in connection with compulsory schools, such as infrastructure. Under the Local Education Agenda (LEA) cooperation is mandated between the municipalities and other government levels. The framework is set by the central government, but regarding the administration, the Dutch education system is quite decentralised. In the Netherlands, lower secondary schools make the majority of the decisions related to their schools. School boards represent the legal authority over one or more schools being responsible for the organisation of the schools (management of personnel and resources, an organisation of instructions and school self-evaluation and quality monitoring). The members of the school boards are very differently in the Netherlands, they can include volunteers (e.g. parents) and/or professional managers. The leadership of the schools can be shared between many officials in larger schools and in secondary schools teachers are also involved in the management of schools.

For public and private schools equal funding is allocated from the central budget on the basis of the number of students enrolled. Those private schools cannot apply for public subsidies that are financed from private sources 100%. Schools are funded from public money if and only if they meet certain requirements. Primary and secondary schools receive block grants from municipalities on the basis of the number of students attending the particular school (these block grants are provided by the state to the municipalities that later give it to the schools). Then the school boards can decide on how to use these grants. The block grants are for the staffing and operating costs of the schools. Schools with children from a disadvantaged background and with special needs can apply for additional funding. All the schools can get additional money for specific educational purposes, such as for students at risk of dropping out of education. In secondary vocational schools block grants are received directly from the government and students pay tuition fees. 80% of the number of block grants are determined on the basis of the number of students enrolled, the rest is determined on the basis of the number of certificates awarded. Because of the decreasing population and financial resources school boards need to learn to use the funds more effectively.

Public procurement system is highly decentralized in the Netherlands as all the contracting authorities are responsible for their own procurement processes regardless of their level of authority.

However, at the central level, the only authority regarding public procurement procedures is the Ministry of Economic Affairs. The functions of the Ministry are:

- to draft procurement legislation
- to interface with the European Union
- to control the compliance with the law

The Public Procurement Expertise Centre (PIANOo) also belongs to the Ministry of Economic Affairs. PIANOo is a network of 3 500 Dutch public procurement experts and tendering professionals who share their best practices and experiences. PIANOo hosts an online forum, it also organizes conferences, training sessions, and meetings and is responsible for the operation of the TenderNed e-procurement platform.

A mediator body is the Commission of Public Procurement Experts that belongs to the organization of the Ministry of Economic Affairs. It has the right to formulate non-binding advice how to resolve claims in case of disagreement between the economic actor and the contracting authority. The claims are also handled by the Civil Courts, in which decisions can be appealed to the Court of Appeal and ultimately to the Supreme Court.

Although supervisory responsibilities are decentralized the Authority for Consumers and Markets (ACM) reviews the procedures in order to reveal possible unfair competition, and this body has the right to impose fines. Moreover, at the level of contracting authorities reviews of economic efficiency and legal compliance are carried out on a yearly basis.

2.22 Poland

The education system in Poland is decentralised and is governed by two ministries and it is administered by a three-tier public administration system. The Ministry of National education sets the national education policy, the legal framework and curricula and it also checks and validates the textbooks. The Ministry of National education is also responsible for the supervision of regional assessment bodies from primary and secondary schools. The Ministry of Science and Higher Education determines the school standards at tertiary level. There are several other bodies participating in the education government system:

- the Centre for Education Development provides support to schools regarding their statutory tasks and the improvement of their performance. it also gives support to teachers for developing their pedagogical skills
- the National Centre for Supporting Vocational and Continuing Education and the Educational Research Institute are both responsible for raising standards and promoting national education policy setting
- at the regional level, the national education policy is implemented by the education Superintendent Offices, which main tasks include the pedagogical supervision of public and private schools and teacher training institutions
- the Central Examinations Commission implements external student assessments and controls the work of eight regional examination branches
- the General Council of Science and Higher Education, the Polish Accreditation Committee and other bodies help the Ministry of Science and Higher Education
- there are other stakeholders (mainly association bodies and trade unions) such as the Polish Teachers' Union, the National Association of School Management Staff and some non-governmental organisations, e.g. the Centre for Civic Education

Municipalities, districts and regional authorities have separate responsibilities in the education system of Poland. Municipalities have to establish the pre-primary, primary and lower secondary schools and have a high autonomy in the financial decisions. Districts are responsible for the higher secondary educational institutions

(general, basic vocational schools, technical upper secondary schools and special schools). Regional authorities have a coordinating function in the implementation of national education policy and they have to ensure the supervision from a pedagogical point of view.

In Poland the schools have a relatively high autonomy in decision-making, they can individually decide on teaching practices, assessment policies, the content of courses, the employment of school staff and the distribution of the merit-based and needs-based scholarships.

Public school funding in Poland is determined on an annual basis by the central government and it is fixed in the Budget Act. Then the funds are being distributed by regional and local authorities, institutions. These bodies have quite a high level of independence in deciding the allocation criteria of the funds. The intermediary bodies receive lump sums from the central government on the basis of the number of teaching staff, students and other factors such as the needs of the particular age groups, specific courses provided in the schools another type of are the school is located in (e.g. remote area). Local authorities have the right to give funding to the schools from their own financial resources mainly for salaries of teachers. However, these resources are quite limited.

Public procurement system in Poland is decentralized however there is one primary policy, executive and oversight body: the Public Procurement Office (PPO). PPO does not fulfil any purchasing tasks and roles. The organizational structure of the PPO includes the President, a permanent staff and the Public Procurement Council which is an advisory body. The Public Procurement Office has the following functions:

- to draft procurement legislation
- to gather data and process these data in order to formulate an analysis, then to publish annual reports of the gathered information
- to disseminate procurement guidance
- to maintain the digital Public Procurement Bulletin

The 10-15 members of the Public Procurement Council are appointed by the Prime Minister in order to provide professional advice and consultancy to the PPO.

The Public Procurement Office also performs controls of award processes and in case of irregularities it recommends to halt, modify ongoing procedures, or it can apply to the Court to nullify an award decision.

Appeals can be submitted to the National Appeal Chamber (KIO) that acts as the first instance body. KIO is a non-judicial review body that belongs to the Public Procurement Office. Against the decisions of the KIO appeals can be sent to the regional courts and ultimately to the Supreme Court.

The use of public resources is reviewed by the Supreme Audit Office (SAO) in terms of effectiveness, economic efficiency and benefit of the Polish State. The SAO reports to the Parliament, but the content of these reports are also publicly available.

For contracts that are co-funded by the European Union, the oversight institutions are the managing authorities, intermediary authorities of the second level, and the Centre for EU Transport projects.

2.23 Portugal

The education system and the governance of it centralised in Portugal. The main responsible authority is the Ministry of Education and Science with tasks:

- to define the curriculum
- to determine the guidelines for national examinations
- to outline the teachers' recruitment strategy and deployment strategy
- to form the budget at pre-primary, primary, secondary and tertiary levels

There are other bodies involved in the governance of the education system listed below:

- ministry services, e.g. the General Secretariat, six Directorate Generals (in areas: school administration, education, planning and financial management, education and science statistics, higher education and schools), the Educational Evaluation Institute, the National Agency for Qualification and Vocational Education, the Scientific and Pedagogical Council for Continuous Training, the General Inspectorate of Education and Science
- advisory bodies that stimulate the participation of stakeholder groups, such as the National Education Council, Schools Council, parents' organisations, the National Association of Portuguese Municipalities and teachers' professional associations
- other bodies participating in the governance of tertiary education: the Coordinating Council for Higher Education, the Coordinating Council for Polytechnic Institutions and the National Agency for Evaluation and Accreditation of Higher Education Programs

In the last ten years, municipalities have been given more and more responsibility and authority over decisions on pre-primary, primary and lower secondary levels. Thus now municipalities can make decisions regarding the offer of extracurricular activities, providing school meals and transportation to the students, managing the infrastructure of the schools and even in hiring and dismissing of non-teaching staff. However, at the upper secondary level, there is no decision-making right in the hands of local or regional authorities at the moment.

The schools at all levels are financed from the central state budget with some responsibility of the Ministry of Education and Science. Funds for public schools are allocated directly from the state budget, while funds granted to those private schools that have a charter agreement are partially allocated by the Ministry. Municipalities also have got a considerable role in the financing mechanism, as they cover the costs of managing educational facilities, transport and extra-curricular activities.

In the Portuguese government, a decentralised system was formed with a central government and two independent regions (Azores and Madeira) enjoying legislative autonomy. The Ministry of Economy is the main body in the Public procurement system in Portugal formulating and developing the national procurement policy. The Ministry of Finance is also an important factor in the public procurement system, and both ministries ensure the compliance with statistical reporting of the procurement system.

The central purchasing body is the eSPap, which manages large framework contracts through which central government agencies are obliged to purchase standardised products (e.g. vehicles, paper goods). eSPap provides various services to any public body that joins the National System of Public Procurement. The Portuguese Competition Authority (PCA) ensures the compliance with competition rules in Portugal.

There is another external oversight body that plays an important role: the Court of Auditors which is a fully independent judicial body and is entitled to issue sanctions for any irregularities overall Portuguese administration institutions.

The internal oversight bodies are the Inspectors Generals within every ministr.

2.24 Romania

At the national level, the administration and management of the education and training system is the responsibility of the Ministry of Education, Research, Youth and Sports. Its task is to establish the education policy based on cooperation and consultation with other responsible ministries. There are experts' bodies and consultative bodies that provide support for the Ministry in decision making (e.g. the National Council for Education Reform). During the consultations, other stakeholders are also involved such as national teachers' professional associations, teachers' unions, and students' associations.

The County School Inspectorates ensure the control and overview at the local level of the legislation and evaluation of the education system. Its tasks include also the implementation of the national education policy. Tertiary education is also

controlled by the Ministry of Education, Research, Youth and Sports, but universities and other tertiary education institutions are autonomous.

During the decentralisation process many institutions external to the Ministry of Education, Research, Youth and Sports were founded:

- the National Centre for Curriculum and Evaluation of Pre-tertiary Education
- the National Service for Assessment and Evaluation
- the National Centre for TVET Development
- the National Commission for Pre-tertiary Education Evaluation and Accreditation
- the National Council for Financing Public Pre-tertiary Education
- the National Centre for In-service Training of the Pre-tertiary Education Staff
- the National Centre for Recognition and Equivalence of Diplomas

County School Inspectorates act at the regional level and they can design and implement their own budget provided by the Ministry of Education, Research, Youth and Sports. The Inspectorates are obliged to make annual evaluations about the education system in their region and they have to determine and create the management plan for the next year including the planned activities, objectives, resources and responsibilities. The management plan then is discussed with the appointed consultative bodies and they have to be approved by the council of the Inspectorates. If the management plan is approved, it becomes compulsory for the actors in the management system of the respective region.

At the local level, local public domains play an important role in the maintenance of the education system, as according to law all the public school building belong to them and public Pre-tertiary education institutions are financed from local budgets (town, commune and in the case of special schools county). There are certain costs that are covered from the central budget through the County School Inspectorates.

Local public administration authorities are responsible for the proper operation of the school education in their territory.

Funding includes three different types of funding:

- basic funding is provided by the state on the basis of the number of students enrolled at pre-primary, primary and secondary levels for public schools
- complementary funding
- additional funding

In private schools, parents have to pay tuition fees determined by the Administration Council of each school.

Schools are governed by their Administration Councils, the head teachers and the deputy's head teachers. They cooperate in the decision making process with the Teachers' Council, the Parents' Committee and local public administrative authorities. The Administration Council are set up by the following members:

- the head of the school
- the deputy head(s) of the school
- the chief accountant
- elected representatives of the teachers
- a representative of the parents
- a representative of the local public administration authority
- representatives of the economic agents

The representative of the teachers' union takes place in the meetings as an observer.

The administration council of high-schools and post high schools also include students' representatives.

In Romania, the government and the public procurement system are both very centralised. However, there are numerous institutions playing a considerable role in the system. The National Public Procurement Agency (ANAP) is the main public body in the public procurement system belonging to the Ministry of Finance. ANAP is responsible for legislation and policy-making, and it fulfils executive and monitors functions. Being responsible for the monitor means that the National Public Procurement Agency implement ex-ante controls on all the tenders regardless of their value.

Another important organisation is the National Council for Solving Complaints (CNSC). CNSC is the first instance administrative body that has jurisdictional power over public procurement procedures. The main objective of the Council is to ensure the compliance of the contracting authorities with the respective legislations. In order to achieve the compliance the NCSC examine the complaints about any irregularities. It has got the authority to force the contracting authorities to take corrective actions. An appeal can be issued at the Court of Appeal against the decision of the NCSC and the decision about the appeal is binding for all the parties involved.

The main oversight body is the Romanian Court of Accounts that implementing ex-post audits and controls of the planning, management and use of public financial sources during the public procurement process. It has to report its findings to the National Public Procurement Agency and to the National Anticorruption Directorate (DNA). DNA has the right to issue and sanction if the irregularity is justified. The external audit of EU-co-funded projects is implemented by the Audit Authority within the Court of Accounts. Another important actor is an autonomous administrative body, the Competition Council that is responsible for protecting and stimulating competition in Romania. It fulfils its monitoring role through the Bid Rigging Module (BRM) that analyses control reports in order to identify potential anticompetitive actions during the public procurement processes. If they find any suspicious case, the can implement an investigation on the selected processes and it also has the right to issue sanctions and fines.

2.25 Slovakia

The Slovak education system is strongly decentralized as three levels of government are responsible for it: the central government, the regional and municipal authorities and the schools themselves. At the central government level the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic determines the policies for pre-primary education, primary education, secondary education and tertiary education as well. Its task is to support educational facilities and lifelong learning, to set the framework for schooling, to manage the network of schools, to allocate financial resources and also to monitor school compliance

and student performance. There are other central bodies appointed to support the education system in the Slovak Republic:

- the National Institute of Education is responsible for the management of schools and educational activities of teachers from the professional and methodological point of view
- the National School Inspectorate overviews the quality of pedagogical management, education and material-technical conditions acting on behalf of the state
- the National Institute for Certified Educational Measurements manages assessments in the country and the participation of the country in international assessments
- the National Institute of Vocational Education is responsible for strategies and concepts of VET
- the Methodology and Pedagogy Centre is appointed to provide educational activities for teachers and non-teaching staff of schools
- the Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information is a specialised scientific library

Self-governing regions and municipalities are the founders of public schools, thus they have got a direct influence on the organisation of them. Pre-primary, primary and lower secondary schools are managed by municipalities, while upper secondary schools are under the management of regional authorities. The majority of the decisions are taken still at the central level, however, the autonomy of schools in the development of the curriculum has been increased. The lower secondary schools make individually 59% of the decisions. Schools are the employers of teachers and non-teaching staff as well. In the school's management, the school leader is helped by the School Board and other advisory bodies, such as pedagogical board and subject committees.

In the Slovak Republic funding is allocated to school founders by the state, then these resources are allocated to the schools. There are founders operating several schools, and they have the freedom to reallocate a certain proportion among these schools. There is some exception being directly financed at the local level: the kindergartens, language schools and basic art schools.

The funding that is allocated to the founders is determined on the basis of the student number and the type of school. Additional funding is provided for example for children with special needs, or for bilingual study. Schools receive dedicated resources for teaching assistants, contributions for the education of socially disadvantaged students and vouchers to finance the extra-curricular education of students.

Public procurement system in Slovakia is highly centralized with one central administration institution: the Office for Public Procurement (UVO). Its functions are:

- to exercise the legislative and regulatory authority
- to draft and monitor the implementation of the Public Procurement Act and other related legislation
- to provide ex-ante review of public procurement documents
- to perform oversight activities
- to publish statistical information and training and guidance for contracting authorities and suppliers
- to manage the online portal
- to act as the first instance review body with the right to impose fines

The Supreme Audit Office (NKU) is the external control body that reviews the public procurement processes in terms of compliance with the legislation and issues recommendations to the Office for Public Procurement.

The central purchasing body is the Ministry of the Interior for commonly available goods, services and works. The fair competition is defended through the Antimonopoly Office that works as an independent body with responsibilities of investigating bid rigging and cartels.

In Slovakia, appeals should be reported to the contracting authority first then it can be brought before the Office for Public Procurement (acting as the first instance body). If the disagreement cannot be solved to the satisfaction of both parties, the second instance is exercised by the Council of the Office. Ultimately the appeal can be submitted to the Regional Appeal Courts and to the Supreme Court as the last recourse instance.

2.26 Slovenia

In Slovenia, the responsibilities regarding education are shared between the central government and the schools. The central government determines the education policy, while the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport are appointed to draft, evaluate and also to implement regulations and to outline national programmes. It is the main authority over pre-primary schools, compulsory primary schools and lower secondary schools, as well as upper secondary schools, adult and higher education institutions. The Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities is responsible for ensuring the well-being of students. The Ministry of Finance is the responsible authority over education budget.

There are other bodies appointed to participate in the management and implementation of education in Slovenia:

- the National Education Institute of the Republic of Slovenia implements and controls programmes and practices in kindergartens and schools, moreover it also performs research and organizes and implements training for professionals
- the Inspectorate for Education and Sport of the Republic of Slovenia performs reviews in Slovenian schools and kindergartens
- the National Examinations Centre coordinates the national assessments and ensures the integration within the international certification system
- the Institute of the Republic of Slovenia for Vocational Education and Training is responsible for accomplishing research regarding VET system and coordinating the programmes, training for teachers and controls
- the professional development of school leaders and candidates are organized by the National School of Leadership in Education
- the responsible organization for education-related research and surveys is the Educational Research Institute
- there are several councils of experts established in order to support the planning process and the implementation of education policy (e.g. the Council of the Republic of Slovenia for General Education, Vocational and Professional Education, Adult Education and Higher Education)

- the Slovenian Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education ensures the quality standards in the field of higher education

In the Republic of Slovenia, schools can take 58% of the decisions, but they have got less control over curricula and assessment issues compared to the OECD average. Schools generally can make their own decision in issues regarding resource management.

The schools in Slovenia are managed by school leaders and governed by their school councils. At all levels, school councils include a representative of founders, employees and parents, while in upper secondary schools school council also includes students' representatives. The main responsibilities of the school council are to appoint and dismiss the school leader, to determine the school development plan and the annual work plans and also to coordinate the implementation of the plans.

In the Republic of Slovenia, schools are funded by the state and by municipalities as well. The state provides financial resources for salaries of teachers and non-teaching staff, for material costs (e.g. teaching and learning materials, textbooks, meals, in-service training of staff). Municipalities are mainly responsible for covering the operational expenditure and the transportation costs of students. If a municipality is not able to cover these costs from its own budget it can receive additional help from the central budget. In the case of upper secondary, vocational and tertiary education the institutions are financed directly from the state budget.

The public procurement system is relatively centralised in Slovenia. The main legislative authority is the Ministry of Public Administration, in which the Public Procurement Directorate (PPD) carries out the majority of the functions regarding public procurement:

- it develops policy and implementation
- it works on the harmonisation of Slovenian law with EU regulations
- it develops the e-procurement tools and services

- it provides and develops the professional training
- it makes an analysis of the public procurement system
- it fulfils all the supportive functions
- it performs joint purchasing for government entities

The National Review Commission for Reviewing Public Procurement Award Procedures (DKOM) monitors compliance with procurement legislation and also acts as a review body. It is entitled to annual award decisions, and it is also authorized to formulate binding recommendations on how a disagreement regarding procurement processes should be resolved.

The highest authority for supervising public spending in Slovenia is the Court of Audit that has the authority to review any on-going or past process.

2.27 Spain

In Spain, regions have autonomy regarding education government. The central government determines the legislation through developing principles, objectives and the organisation of different education levels, the content of teaching and the taught subjects through the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport (MECD). The Ministries of Education (or their departments) have the right to design the education policy and to develop their education system in their own region. The management of the regional education systems also falls under the authority of the respective Ministry of Education in the region. There are other bodies that play important role in the governance of the education system:

- the regional ministries and the central Ministry of education, Culture and Sport cooperate through the Education Sector Conference in order to design coherent education policies
- within the MECD the State Secretariat for Education, Vocational Training and Universities defines qualification for the education system and teachers
- other education stakeholders such as teachers' unions, school owners and students' representatives work together through the State School Board, which also gives advice regarding the education programme, school funding and school-level innovation
- the National Conference of University Deans guides the university sector

- the Higher Board of Arts Education provides advice regarding the respective area
- Regional Councils for Vocational Training is in charge of the evaluation of the VET system
- Local authorities and municipalities have the competence on the maintenance & caretakers (concierge) of Primary Schools. Some municipalities also are in charge of nurseries (0-3 years old). This is no compulsory education and in Spain there are some private nurseries and some public (managed by municipalities).

Due to the decentralised system, regional authorities have responsibilities to a great extent in the following areas:

- school maintenance
- organisations and delivery of education
- making decisions on school funding, and part of the curriculum

In the decision making the process at the school level, the School Councils also participate including representatives of teachers' body, students' body, the town council, parents and non-teaching staff.

In Spain (similarly to other European Union Member States) education is mainly funded from public financial resources, however in this country, the 17 regions have higher autonomy in making the financial decisions. The regional government can decide how to allocate their annual budget to different schools. Public schools receive a small amount of funding on the basis of the number of students enrolled. Publicly funded private schools can receive funding from public financial sources if they meet certain requirements.

The public procurement system of Spain is highly decentralized partly because of their decentralized political system. There is a single legal framework, but a wide diversity of contracting management and oversight bodies. The Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations is in charge of the national public procurement policy through two bodies:

- the Directorate General for State Assets is responsible for the general regulations of public procurement, the national strategy for e-procurement and the e-procurement platform
- the Directorate General for Rationalisation and Centralisation of Procurement harmonises and centralises the national public procurement, operates as the central purchasing body for the State administration and state-owned entities

The State Consultative Board on Administrative Procurement is autonomous, but it belongs to the Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations. This Board provides legal advice and guidance in order to improve the quality of public contracts in terms of administrative, technical and financial aspects. Almost all region has its own consultative board which are obliged to create reports and recommendations to improve the public procurement process. There are platforms which help the administrations of tenders, collects the information about the awarded contracts helping the contracting authorities: Official Registry of Tenderers and Contractors of the State (ROLECE), Public Contracts Registry (RCP).

The main oversight bodies are the followings:

- the National Court of Auditors
- the General State Comptrollers
- the General Regional Comptrollers

Comptrollers on both state and regional levels conduct internal audits in order to ensure legality and efficiency.

The Central Administrative Court of Contractual Appeals (TACRC) is entitled to impose sanctions and fines.

2.28 Sweden

In Sweden, the education system is highly decentralized with the overall responsibility of the central government (including the curriculum development, defining the national objectives and guidelines). Within the government the responsibilities are shared between two ministries: the Ministry of Education and Research and three autonomous national agencies:

- the Swedish National Agency for Education support and evaluates the work of the municipalities and schools, creates national statistics and coordinates the work of municipalities and schools with the work of the Ministry in determining the national goals and curriculum
- the Swedish Schools Inspectorate approves the establishment of new schools, ensures that municipalities and schools follow the laws and regulations developed at the central level
- the National Agency for Special Needs Education coordinates the efforts of the government regarding students with special educational needs

Municipalities are responsible for Public Schools and they cooperate in the Swedish Association of Local Authorities and Regions, while independent schools belong under the authority of the respective school's organiser and these organisers work together in the Swedish Association of Independent Schools. Both associations are in charge of implementing educational activities, organising and operating school services, allocating resources. They also ensure that the national goals determined for education are met.

Every municipality is governed by the Municipal Assembly, which appoints an education committee to govern the education system in their territory. School leaders of the municipal schools submit their reports to the education committee.

In Sweden there is no privately funded school, schools are financed mainly from municipal taxes and approximately 15% of the budget is allocated from central financial sources. Independent schools also receive funding from the municipality of the student's hometown. The funding is based on the number of students enrolled.

Schools at all levels (pre-primary, primary, secondary) are financed through the mechanism described above. Municipalities have the autonomy to decide the allocation of funding between different schools, thus schools from a worse socio-economic territory can receive more financing. After the funding is allocated, the

schools have got the right to divide this funding into the different expenditure categories in order to ensure that the needs of the students are met.

Sweden has a relatively decentralised public procurement system with two main institutions regarding procurement policy:

- the Swedish Competition Authority (KKV) which operates within the Ministry of Enterprise and Innovation (MoE) and is a supervisory body being entitled to overview public procurement processes in terms of compliance with the law and efficiency, and it can forward the found irregularities to the administrative courts for investigation. KKV also provides administrative and methodological help to contracting authorities and economic operators
- the National Agency for Public Procurement (UHM) which belongs to the Ministry of Finance and it develops and maintains support functions to public procurement. It also promotes sustainable procurement from the social and environmental point of view and the innovative public procurement procedures.

The Swedish Agency for Economic and Regional Growth (SAERG) (within the Ministry of Industry) is a national government agency appointed to promote sustainable development and regional growth. It provides help for enterprises to become more competitive through knowledge, networking and financing.

The main oversight body is the National Audit Office (NAO) which performs external audits and its findings are forwarded directly to the Parliament together with recommendations for the better and more efficient use of the public funds.

The body that is entitled to issue sanctions is the Administrative Courts of First Instance. Against its decision appeal can be issued to the Administrative Court of Appeal, so decisions may be reviewed by the Supreme Administrative Court.

In Sweden, the central purchasing body is the NPS operating under the Ministry of Finance. It is the central purchasing body for state administrations and state-owned entities. Moreover, the Swedish National Financial Management Authority manages framework agreements for administrative systems and associated services.

2.29 United Kingdom

In the United Kingdom includes four countries: England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales. The education system in England, Northern Ireland and Wales are similar, but in Scotland, there are some differences regarding the structure and the qualifications. The main authorities and institution playing an important role in the education systems are the following:

- All the four countries have a government department or directorate that is responsible for the educational policies: the Department for Education in England, the Department of Education in Northern Ireland, the Scottish Government in Scotland and the Department for Education and Skills in Wales.
- In England and Northern Ireland, a separate department of government is responsible for policies relating the vocational education and adult learning
- In England, Northern Ireland and Wales the qualifications are the responsibility of the National Qualifications Framework, while in Scotland the responsible authority is the Scottish Qualification Authority
- the student assessment policies and national data collections from schools are the responsibilities of the central government departments mentioned above in Wales, Northern Ireland and Scotland, while in England it is the responsibility of the Standards and Testing Agency within the Department for Education
- In each country different organisations are responsible for the reviews of schools: in England the Office for Standards in Education, in Northern Ireland the Education and Training Inspectorate, in Wales the Inspectorate for Education and Training and in Scotland the Education Scotland
- In Scotland and England the development of teachers and school leaders and the implementation of certain policies concerning them is quite similar: in England, the National College for Teaching and Leadership is appointed for this task, in Scotland a similar organization. In Northern Ireland, a local education agency provides the licensed version of the English programme for school leader candidates

- there are several other stakeholders such as funding councils, national institutions, industry groups, different teacher unions, government associations and parent groups

Most policies are determined within the four countries, and no policy decisions are taken on the level of the United Kingdom. This means that basically the sovereignty of all the four countries are ensured. There are several intergovernmental arrangements and cooperation between national governments, however, they are limited.

In England and Scotland, most decisions regarding education are taken at local level and at the school level. In England, some authority (e.g. for school place planning) has been maintained at the local governments, but the majority of the decisions are taken at the school level. However, in Scotland, it is a recent movement and process that the decision-making rights of the schools have been increased through the delivery of curriculum and general policy as well as resource decisions being shared with local authorities.

The funding mechanisms of schools are different in each of the four countries of the United Kingdom. Basically, there are three categories of educational institutions in all the four countries:

- publicly funded schools
- private government-dependent schools (academies and free schools in England, and a very few examples in Scotland)
- independent private schools

Publicly funded schools get financial resources from the government and local authorities as well, while they have a very low level of self-income. Academies and free schools are funded directly by national governments (but they are independent of local authorities). Independent private schools do not get any subsidies neither from the national governments nor from local authorities, thus they are funded from private financial resources. Most of the students attend publicly

funded schools where they get the education without any tuition fees, and parents have to pay only for extra-curricular activities and school supplies.

The public procurement system in the United Kingdom is unique in the European Union due to the legislative structure of the country.

The main procurement institution for England, Wales and Northern Ireland is the Efficiency and Reform Group (ERG) with many functions:

- it transfers EU directives
- it handles cases of breach
- it overviews the procurement activity for value
- it provides guidance and training for contracting authorities.

In Scotland, the Scottish Procurement and Commercial Directorate (SPD) has similar functions. In Scotland, in every case, the contracting authority is responsible for the fulfilment of the public procurement procedure.

The Crown Commercial Service (CCS) is one of the central purchasing bodies. The aim of the operation of the CCS is to improve the economic efficiency of the purchasing through the aggregation of purchasing power. The Crown Commercial Service provides advice to other government departments and plays a leading role in the procurement policy of the United Kingdom. There are many other central purchasing bodies at both regional and local levels.

The National Audit Office (NAO) is an oversight body that performs overviews in terms of economic efficiency. The NAO reports to the Parliament, hence it does not publish any annual reports.

Proceeding against contracting authorities can be started in the High Court of England, Wales and Northern Ireland, or in Scotland in the Court of Session or Sheriff Court. These judicial authorities are entitled to issue penalties and even to invalidate decisions in cases of irregularities or breaches. The decision of the above-listed authorities can be appealed in the Civil Division of the Court of Appeal and ultimately in the Supreme Court of the United Kingdom.

3. Procurement of ICT solutions in the LEA partner countries

In this part, more detailed information is given on the countries that participate in the Learning Technology Accelerator project. The partners from Austria, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Portugal, Spain and Sweden have prepared descriptions about the ICT procurements for educational purposes in their country as part of the previous project of the consortium – IMAILE.

In the LEA project, a questionnaire has been conducted including questions about the practice of procurements for educational purposes. The answers are analysed in this section, providing additional information on the system of purchasing ICT in education in the case of the countries of LEA partner organisations: Austria, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Portugal, Spain and Sweden.

3.1 Procurement of ICT tools in Austria

In the Learntech Accelerator project, primary and lower secondary education is the main focus point, in this regard the maintenance responsibilities are summarized in the following graphic:

Figure 4: Austria educational institutions maintenance responsibilities, Source: Austrian Court of Audits

The local authority is responsible for the maintenance of infrastructure in the educational institution, however, the principal of the school has the right to make suggestions for procurement. The decision is taken on the level of the local authority, and every contracting authority is responsible for the management of its own procurement. This regulation also applies to the ICT procurement processes. The teachers have a consulting role in the procurement procedure and how the public tender will look like. All the schools have got dedicated panels where needs and stakeholder interests are discussed among the teachers, external stakeholders, principals and parents /pupil representatives (Schulgemeinschaftsausschuss). Then the principal fulfils connecting functions between the educational institution and the local authority. The principal has the right to lead the discussion in the Schulgemeinschaftsausschuss, and has a consulting role for the local authority, however, he/she does not have any power of decision.

3.2 Procurement of ICT tools in Finland

In Finland, the education system is particularly decentralized. The central governments allocate funds to every community on the basis of the number of students. All the schools are independent and have the right to make their own decision. Local education institutes even have the right to launch public procurements in order to purchase their own ICT tools for educational purposes. But many agreements have been made in order to centralize the public procurement of ICT solutions.

The procurement process consists of the following steps:

- Feasibility study and needs analysis of the system
- Tender for the industry in public info channels (if the price of the tool to purchase is small enough the schools have got the right to buy it straight, without tender)
- Evaluation of the offers
- Decision

In the implementation process, there are differences between the communities on the basis of their level of development. If the community is advanced then the

implementation process is the responsibility of the education ICT centres. In any other case, the ICT departments are responsible.

Teachers also play an active role, they create and formulate the contents, needs and usage descriptions. Generally, in Finland, the schools try to get all the new software, solutions or services to be tested by the teachers before starting the procurement processes. The aim is to provide teachers with the opportunity to try the new solutions in their daily work and see the benefits first hand.

In Finland, the in-service training is considered extremely important. There are teachers trained as peer trainers for their colleagues in new areas. Since all the schools are independent, if the principal of a particular school does not support the procurement and use of new technology, then the teachers could not carry it out. Therefore in most schools teachers aim at involving principals in the training. If there is a centralized procurement system, the process is carried out by the principals meeting (decision making), otherwise, it is the task of the principal of the school.

Figure 5 : Procurement process in Finland
Source: own elaboration by Konnevesi

3.3 procurement of ICT tools in Saxony-Anhalt (Germany)

On the basis of the information given by the partners participating in LEA project (and previously in IMAILE project) – Otto von Guericke University and Ministry of Finance of Saxony-Anhalt, the information about the particular process of ICT purchase on the State of Saxony-Anhalt is the following:

The planning period is a fiscal year and not a school year. The different steps are:

- Members of teachers' conference for specified subject submit their requirements to the school principal

- Principle decides whether to submit a request for procurement to school authorities (this decision is based on the budget as well)
- School principal submits a request for ICT solutions to school authorities
- If school authority confirms the funding, three more steps can be implemented:
 - If the procurement costs over 1000 EUR, the school authority manages the procurement process
 - If the procurement costs between 500 EUR and 1000 EUR, the schools can procure the solution itself, but it needs to get three offers for tenders
 - If the procurement costs below 500 EUR, the school can procure the solution on its own and the three offers are not needed
- The invoices are always managed by the school authority.

The role of the teachers in the procurement process is very restricted as they can make the request which solution to be purchased, but they cannot take part in the decision making.

In Germany, school authorities can define their own way of a procurement process that can differ from the one described above. The school authorities have the right to determine own procurement costs as well.

These rights show how different the public procurement process can be in the different Federal States and why the standardization is almost impossible.

3.4 Procurement of ICT tools in Hungary

In Hungary, the Klebelsberg Centre exercises the authority above schools through the education districts. If a school would like to purchase a new ICT tool or solution, the following procedure has to be implemented:

1. the teachers together with the principal determine their ICT needs
2. the principal sends the need to the leader of the school district
3. the leader of the education district collects the needs of all the schools that it is responsible for and send it to the Klebelsberg Centre
4. in Klebelsberg Centre there are experts who decide which tools or solutions should be purchased and when

This is a semi-centralized and very long process, moreover, the procurement has to follow the regulations regarding ICT solutions in the respective Hungarian law.

One of the most important barriers of using ICT tools in the schools is the lack of knowledge of the teachers. In 2016, the Digital Education Strategy of Hungary was created and in the framework of the implementation considerable effort has been made in the ICT skills development and the improvement of the quality of ICT tools in the classrooms. As part of the implementation in 2017, the MOBIDIK Programme was introduced: it contains a container equipped with modern ICT tools for education – 3D printer, LEGO robots, tablets, Tv with a touch screen, etc. 15 schools were chosen and in each school, the container was used for a week. The programme included training for the teachers in order to learn the use of the different tools. The programme was financed by different Hungarian entities: universities, private companies, associations.

This programme is an important step in the improvement of the ICT use in the schools and in the change of teachers' attitude towards ICT solutions.

3.5 Procurement of ICT tools in Portugal

In case of ICT procurement in Portugal the following institutions have the right to make decisions:

- municipalities
- directors of clusters of schools
- Regional Directorate of schools (5 Regional Directorates exist: Norte, Centro, Alentejo, Lisboa and Algarve)

Local educational institutes are authorized to launch public procurement to buy ICT solutions to the classrooms.

The Code of Public Contracts (CPC) lists five different procedures from which the public procurer can choose according to the specific needs that will contain the subject of the future public contract and to the economic value of the contract.

The five different procedures on the basis of the CPC are the following:

1. Direct Award of Contract: it is a simple process that allows the contracting authority to invite directly one or more entities to bid, then to negotiate with them the aspects of the contract to be signed. There are restrictions when this process can be used:
 - a. if the object of the contract is public works, this procedure can be used in case the estimated maximum price is up to the limit of 150 000 EUR
 - b. if the object of the contract is buying of goods and services, then it can be used in case the estimated maximum price is up to 75 000 EUR
 - c. in case of other contracts, if the estimated maximum price is up to 100 000 EUR
2. Public Tender: it is the main general procedure that involves a total competition where every economic operator interested in the bid can present a tender/proposal. This procedure requires the publication in the official journal of a tender with the specifications of the contract and of the service/product and in the Official Journal of the European Union in the case of public works if the estimated price is higher than 5 000 000 EUR, and in the case of buying goods or services if the estimated price is higher than 130 000 EUR or 200 000 EUR in the event of the promoter is a local authority
3. Limited Tender with pre-qualification: this procedure consists of two phases: the first step is the qualification of bidders, the second step is the tender. This procedure is similar to the Public Tender with an extension of the evaluation procedure aiming to evaluate the technical and financial capacity of the potential bidders in order to select those bidders who might be the more reliable suppliers accordingly to the needs identified and type of contract to be awarded.
4. Negotiation Procedure with Tender: this procedure can only be used in exceptional situations when the object of the tender is, for instance,, financial services, when the technical specifications are impossible to be correctly specified in the tender or when it is not possible to properly establish the price of the services or products.

5. Competitive Dialogue: it is used in cases where the contract to be awarded is highly complex and it is not possible to implement an open tender or a limited tender with pre-qualification. Thus this procedure is for complex sectors that are in constant change, such as the ones involving high technology, where, despite the fact that the needs are known, the technical solutions are not known and the technical specifications difficult to define or even impossible to be defined solely by the public authority.

The most commonly used procedures at the municipal/local level are the Public tender and the Direct Award of Contract. The main steps in both procedures are in the graph below:

Figure 6 : General steps of the procedure for the Common Public Procurement for the awarding of a contract and Direct Award of Contract- Portugal

Teachers are not directly involved in the procurement decisions, but they play an important role in the recognition of the needs of the students, according to the above-detailed practice of needs assessment:

- in the case of pre-primary schools and 1st cycle compulsory education schools (from year 3 to year 10), the school director/principal cooperates with the municipality in the name of the school in order to identify the needs of the students
- in case of 2nd and 3rd cycle of compulsory education institutions and upper secondary schools, the management of the schools is performed by the Ministry of Education. The director/principal of a cluster of schools is responsible for the implementation and management of the procurement process and has autonomy in the decision if the value of the product/service to be purchased is up to 4 500 EUR (+VAT). In all other

cases, the decision making right belongs to the Regional Directorate of schools

- For the schools that are not integrated into clusters, the director/principal is responsible for the dialogue with the services of the local representative of the Regional Directorate of schools.

3.6 Procurement of ICT tools in Spain

In Spain, the Regional Governments are entitled to make public procurement decisions. In the LEA project Viladecans City Council participates from Spain, and in their case, the responsible authority is Catalonia's Regional Government. The educational institutions have the right to use the budget, that remains when the basic functions are already covered, according to their own decisions. Moreover, schools can receive additional funding from city councils, parents' associations and companies. In case of purchasing ICT tools, there are special rules that have to be taken into consideration. The entitled purchasing body was previously the Education Department of Catalonia's Regional Government, now the entitled authority for ICT purchasing is the Telecommunications and Information Technologies Centre (CTTI), that gathers the needs of all the areas (education, health, etc.). After the request is received, the purchase is assessed according to the strategy and budget available, and if approved, the purchase is delivered to the Education Centre. There is a contradiction in the system as Education Centres are entitled by law to make their own decisions regarding ICT procurement. This contradiction has to be resolved.

In the public system, four different procurement methods are allowed, depending on the value of procurement as follows:

1. Minor Contracts: to purchase goods and services with a value up to 18 000 EUR (+VAT). For these contracts, 3 offers have to be gathered and the Local Governing Body approves the purchasing.
2. Negotiated procedure without publicity: it can be used for purchases with values between 18 001 EUR and 60 000 EUR (+VAT). For these contracts, 3 bids have to be asked from the suppliers, the approval of the administrative and technical call documents, Local Governing Body approval and

provisional and final awarding process (final awarding process 20 days after provisional awarding).

3. Open procedure: for purchases with a value of more than 60 001 EUR (+VAT). This method requires a public process with different publicity periods depending on the type of products/services to be purchased.
4. Uniform regulation: these contracts are subject to European directives on public procurement including:
 - public work contracts and works concessions from 5 000 000 EUR
 - Supply contracts up to 130 000 EUR which are awarded by the National Government and linked entities
 - supply contracts up to 200 000 EUR which are awarded by entities, organizations or public sector entities other than mentioned above
 - services contracts up to 130 000 EUR which are awarded by the National Government
 - services contracts up to 200 000 EUR which are awarded by entities, organizations or public sector entities other than the ones listed above

Contracts using the Uniform regulation can be managed only by public procurers, and they have to be published in the Official Journal of the European Union. The contract can be separated into batches of activity, and in this case, each batch can be issued separately. The batches contain different functional units. The batch splitting has to be clearly specified in the call and the supplier can present an offer to one or more batches.

Each school is obliged to elaborate the plan for the inclusion and use of the ICT solutions in the centre called Technology Plan for Learning and Knowledge. This plan includes the strategy and needs of each centre regarding ICT tools: hardware (e.g. Interactive Whiteboards, ICT devices, connectivity) and software (e.g. educational platforms). A group of teachers has to design the Technology Plan for

Learning and Knowledge including the procurement needs regarding ICT. The implementation of the plan is also designed by the centre individually through the Working Committee, in a collaborative way, through Management Board decision, etc. This plan has to be approved both by the teachers and the Principal. Basically, the Principals are the procurers as they are entitled to the procurement at accountancy level. They also have to lead the process and to promote the process.

In the case of private schools, private centre owners exercise decision making power. In private schools proposals are made by the Management Board regarding which ICT tool to purchase and have to be approved by the Principal. In the proposal making process, teachers specialized in the ICT area and teachers with specific knowledge in the area of the subject of the purchase provide advice to the Management Board. The Management Board is entitled to ask for bids from the suppliers, and after the approval of the Principal, the owners of the private centre decide about the offers. The principals are in charge of the design and presentation of the proposal and the request for advice in the area of ICT solutions to decide whether to buy or rent the devices.

The figure below shows the visualised model of Spanish procurement process in public education:

Figure 7 : Procurement process in Spain

3.7 Procurement of ICT tools in Sweden

The educational institutes in Sweden have a purchasing council, where the management together with teachers gather and discuss common needs. In case of coordinated procurement, the decision is delegated to the Municipal Director, CFO or Procurement Officer. In each administration, the decision of the procurement will be made by the administration manager or the political board depending on the value. Teachers and other employees are involved and play an important role in the requirement process, as they formulate demands on suppliers. Teachers are also involved in the evaluation activities. In the future, instead of traditional public procurement, innovative processes will be used, as the public will not ask for products or services that are already developed, instead, they will ask the suppliers to create a solution according to their needs and problems.

Below is a figure showing the way how Halmstad municipality works. In the municipality, different methods and design are used on the basis of the type of the products and services.

Figure 8 : Overview of how works the purchasing of ICT solutions in Sweden (Halmstad)

Source: own elaboration by Halmstad

3.8 Results of the questionnaire

Altogether 20 organizations provided responses to the questions. The responses given by organizations from the same country will create the basis of the conclusions about that particular country. If the types of the respondent organization are different, then conclusions can be subtracted what is the difference between their answers and opinions.

On the graph below the number of respondents from each country can be seen:

Figure 9 : The number of respondents from each country

The questionnaire has been created in order to obtain more detailed information about the situation regarding public procurement of ICT solutions in education in all the LEA partners' countries separately. Therefore conclusion on the average situation or practice regarding this kind of procurement will not be presented in this report.

In Austria, the schools do not exercise decision making right in case of educational technology purchases. For primary schools and lower secondary schools, the municipality of their area is authorized to make this decision, while for upper secondary schools the appointing authority is the federal government. The main source for these procurement is the own budget. According to the answer of an Austrian respondents, the price and the combination of the technology with training, that help to use the technology, are extremely important factors that are taken into consideration in case of an educational technology tool procurement. The opinion of the school/teachers is only slightly important, while the following four factors are also important:

- time saved for teachers
- compatibility with the already used systems/software
- teachers already have got the necessary skills to use the technology
- technology is beyond state of the art.

The respondent does not know of any Pre-Commercial Procurement process implemented in Austria.

In Belgium, the schools have no right to make decisions regarding procurement of educational technology tools according to the answer of a respondent from Belgium. On the basis of this response, the decision making "communes" do not think that giving the schools the right to decide would hinder the procurement process, but they prefer to keep the decisions regarding learning content and budget centralized. The source of the procurement of educational technology objectives comes principally from national grants. According to the opinion of the respondents, among the seven listed factors, 3 are important- price, compatibility with already used systems & software and the opinion of the schools/teachers, 2 are slightly important in the decision making about the procurement of educational technology tools. According to this response, the following two factors are not important at all: if the technology is beyond state of the art and if it is combined with training that help to use it.

The other representative from Belgium indicated the compatibility with already used systems and software and the fact whether the technology is beyond state of the art as slightly important, while the other five factors were indicated as important ones.

None of the respondents from Belgium knows of any Pre-Commercial Procurement that has been implemented in the country.

In Finland, schools do not have the right to make decisions regarding the question: Which educational technology tool to purchase? Instead, the municipalities have the authority to make these kind of decisions. There is a dedicated budget for the procurement of educational technology tools and the main source are national grants. One respondent from Finland has the opinion that the municipalities think that it would hinder the procurement processes if the schools would have the right to decide. According to the opinion of this respondent, the following factors are extremely important In case of decision about educational technology tools:

- price
- time saved for teachers
- compatibility with already used systems, software
- technology is combined with training that help to use it
- the opinion of the school/teachers

While the remaining two factors (if the technology is beyond the state of the art and if teachers already have got the necessary skills to use the technology) are not important at all.

According to another respondent from Finland, if the value of procurement is low, the teachers can purchase tools themselves from the own budget of different teacher groups. This budget can be used for buying hardware, software or services. However, if a procurement is needed with a considerable value, the process must include the data management department and the practitioners from the field of procurements. The only obstacle in permitting the schools to make a decision on procurement with larger values is that for this process more skill,

knowledge and experience is needed regarding the process of the procurement and the legislative background.

Based on the point of view of the respondent there are 4 important factors in the procurement decision: time saver for teachers, compatibility with already used systems, software, the combination of the technology with training and the opinion of the teachers). According to this opinion, the price is only a slightly important decisive factor.

From the point of view of the third respondent from Finland, among the seven listed decisive factors, 5 are extremely important and the other two are important. It is not surprising that a municipality, that can be also responsible for the procurement, the price of the tool is extremely important.

Another Finnish respondent stated that there are cities in Finland where the primary/secondary schools can order technology (e.g. IT tools) from municipal ICT providers, that handle equipment/software in large scale. Learning materials (even digital materials) can be purchased at the school level.

From the point of view of this respondent, the price is the only decisive factor that is slightly important, all the other 6 factors listed in the questionnaire are important ones.

In Finland, the only Pre-Commercial Procurement carried out before, about which the partners have information, is the IMAILE project in the area of education.

In Germany, the schools were not given the right to decide, which educational technology tool to purchase. This right is exercised by the school owner. The reason for it is that schools owners prefer to keep this right under their authority and they would like the schools to use standardized solutions.

According to a representative from Germany, the three most important factors that are taken into consideration in the decisions are if teachers already have the necessary skills to use the technology, if the educational technology tool is combined with training that help to use them and the opinion of the

school/teachers. The price, time saved for teachers and the compatibility with already used systems or software are also important, while the fact, that the technology is beyond state of the art, is considered only slightly important.

There is a dedicated budget for educational technology procurements financed from national grants.

According to another German respondent, the price is the most important decisive factor, while the fact that the technology is beyond the state of the art is not important at all. The other five factors listed in the questionnaire are considered slightly important.

Beside the Pre-Commercial Procurement, that was carried out in the IMAILE project, the German LEA partners do not know about any procurements that used this innovative process. In IMAILE project, the Ministry of Finance of Saxony-Anhalt was one of the four procurers.

In Hungary, the schools do not exercise a decision making a right, instead, the school districts are authorized to decide, which educational technology will be purchased in the schools. The educational technology purchases carried out previously were mainly financed from European Union Grants. However, in recent years with the introduction of the Digital Education Strategy, more and more investments started in order to provide the schools with ICT tools for educational purposes.

According to the opinion of the Hungarian respondent, the price is one of the most important decisive factors. Another extremely important factor that is taken into consideration in the decision-making process for educational technology purchases is the compatibility with already used systems or software. In the decision, time saver for teachers, the factor if the technology is beyond state of the art, the combination of the technology with trainings that help to use it and the opinion of the teachers, are slightly important decisive factors, while the fact if teachers already have got the necessary skills to use the technology is not important at all.

The respondent does not have knowledge about any Pre-Commercial Procurement that have been implemented in Hungary.

In Italy, the schools have the right to decide which educational technology to purchase, but in the case of schools, the municipality exercises the decision making a right. According to the opinion of an Italian respondent, all the listed decisive factors are important, most of them extremely important. Two of the factors were indicated as “important”: the opinion of the school/teachers and if the technology is beyond state of the art.

There is a dedicated budget for educational technology purchases that is financed from national grants. In Italy, there is a considerable effort for the modernization of primary and secondary education in terms of implementing the technology of the 21st century. The main problem in the schools is the old buildings, thus they consider the creation of modern school spaces as the biggest challenge. The decision making organizations and also the government believe if the spaces provide the possibility for using modern technology, the quality of education will be improved.

According to another Italian representative, the indication of the importance of the listed decisive factors are different from the previously described opinion:

- extremely important: price, teachers already have got the necessary skills to use the technology, technology is combined with training that help to use it, the opinion of the school/teachers
- important: compatibility of already used systems, software
- slightly important: time saver for teachers, technology is beyond the state of the art

There were altogether 3 respondents from Italy, and their opinion is different about the question, whether the decision-making organizations think that the procurement process would be hindered if the schools would get the decision-making rights. In Italy and in every country there are many decision-making

organizations, and they do not share the same opinion on most of the issues. This can cause this difference between the answers, and another determinant is that probably it is not widely communicated what is the standpoint on this topic. The last respondent from Italy thinks that price and time saved for teachers are important decisive factors, the other five factors listed are extremely important.

In Italy, there was previously Pre-Commercial Procurement implemented in the area of health.

In Portugal, the primary and secondary schools have the right to decide which educational technology will be purchased for them. There is a specified budget for the procurement of educational technology, and the main source for these purchases is provided from own financial sources. On the basis of the opinion of a Portuguese respondent, the most important factors taken into consideration during the decision making which educational technology to purchase are the price, the time saved for teachers, the compatibility with already used systems and software, the opinion of the teachers and that the technology is combined with training helping to use it. The other factors are also important, but not to the same extent as the ones listed above.

From the point of view of another Portuguese respondent, the extremely important factors when the decision is made about which educational technology tool to purchase are:

- Price
- Time saved for teachers
- Teachers already have got the necessary skills for using the technology
- The opinion of the school/teachers

From the point of view of the second Portuguese respondent, the bundling with training and the compatibility with already used systems and software are important, while it is only slightly important whether the tool is beyond state of the art.

In Portugal, there was Pre-Commercial Procurement implemented in the area of health.

In Spain the schools have the right to decide about the educational technology procurement, however, some restrictions are set by the regional government that means in some cases only the regional government is authorized to make the decision. The decision making organization thinks that the procurement process would be hindered if schools had the right to decide, which educational technology tool to purchase and use in the school. However the school manages a small budget, but for the investment of considerable value, the regional government exercises the right to decide.

The main financial sources of the educational technology investments are national grants and regional sources. The questionnaire was filled in by two representatives from Spain.

The classification of the decisive factors according to their importance is different from the point of views, however, both of them consider the time saved for teachers and the opinion of the school/teachers important, while the fact if the technology is combined with training that help to use it extremely important.

The differences between the indications of importance are listed below:

- regarding the price the opinions are totally different, as one of the respondents think that is extremely important, the other one considers it not important at all. It could be caused by the priority order: it can evolve in an organization that something is considered important, but if other decisive factors have been taken into consideration, the previously important factor lose its significance
- between the classification of the compatibility with already used systems, and software and the fact if the technology is beyond state of the art there was a small difference
- the factor if teachers have already got the necessary skills to use the technology has been considered extremely important according to one

respondent and not important at all according to the other one. The reason for the difference can be that both respondents marked the training for technology as extremely important, and considering this the importance of the present skill set could be important however it can be only learned as well. Thus the answer to this question depends on from which side the respondent thinks the question over.

The IMAILE project had a procurer from Spain – Viladecans City Council – and it is the only Pre-Commercial Procurement implemented in the country which the Spanish LEA project partners know of.

In Sweden, the primary/secondary schools have the right to make decisions about educational technology procurement, for which there is a dedicated budget. However there are some tools the schools are obliged to use as a standard, and they do not have any right to change them. The main source for these procurements are the taxes. One of the Swedish respondents, who answered the questionnaire, do not think that the involvement of schools in the decision-making process would have hindered the procurement processes. Regarding the importance of the different factors in the decision making, the most important ones are price, time saved for teachers and training provided in order to help to use the technology. It can be stated that it is only slightly important if the teachers have got the necessary skills to use the procured tool, the important factor is to provide some training for the teachers.

According to the opinion of the other representative from Sweden, the two most important factors in deciding which educational technology to purchase is the time saved for teachers and if the technology is beyond state of the art. These two factors can be connected: if a technology used for teaching goes far beyond the state of the art, it is a basic requirement to save teachers' time.

In Sweden, there were Pre-Commercial Procurements implemented before, one of them was the IMAILE project. Other ones were managed in the areas of health and energy.

From a regional point of view, there are cases where the municipality organized its system in a way that schools have not got the right to individually decide which educational technology to purchase, instead of the municipality exercises this right. From the regional point of view, the compatibility of the to be procured technology with already used systems and software is indeed important, but it is not important at all if the technology is beyond state of the art.

The opinions are the same about the importance of price and time saved for the teachers as well as if the technology is combined with training helping the teachers to use the technology.

Figure 10: The average of the respondents' answers regarding the importance of the listed factors
Source: own source

Summarizing the result of the questionnaire, even within a country there could be differences in the decisive factors and the decision-making system regarding educational technology tool public procurements. However, most of the respondents consider price as one of the most important factors that are taken

into consideration, but the average of the classification does not show considerable differences between the importance of factors. The reason is, that the absolutely different answers create a balance for the average result. However, the analysis and description in the case of all the LEA partner countries show the main characteristics in issues the questionnaire contains questions about.

4. Conclusion

In the previous chapters, the European arena regarding educational technology procurement was described through collecting primary and secondary data for all the 28 Member States of the European Union.

For the description of the education and public procurement systems of the member states, publicly available reports and reviews were used as secondary data collection in the preparation of this document. On the basis of these sources, it can be stated that all the member states have different systems regarding the governance and authority of the system of educational institutions. With the help of these analysis, we were able to draw a general picture of the present situation of the above-mentioned system in the European Union.

Hence the considerable differences according to the dimension of the level of centralization we can classify the countries into two groups: centralized and decentralized countries. The table below contains this classification. The classification was made on the basis of the decision-making rights in the education system taking into consideration the effect of the schools' opinion on the procurement. If in a country schools have a considerable effect on the decision which tool to purchase it was marked as decentralized. In other cases when the decision-making authority lays absolutely in the hands of a central authority the system was marked as centralized.

Figure 11 *Centralized and decentralized education decision making systems in the European Union*

Source: own compilation based on the secondary data collected

The secondary data sources were completed with primary data collection through the information provided of the organizations participating in the LEA project. This improved the information content of the report, as the organizations gathered data not only from publicly available sources but on the basis of their own practice and experience as well. Among the partners, there are municipalities that are involved (at least to some extent) in the public procurement processes of ICT tools in their area. Thu they were able to describe different points of view: the users' point of view, the decision makers' point of view, the point of view of an authority. The questionnaire was designed in order to obtain the most important characteristics regarding the decisions and the decision-making rights in each of the LEA member countries. From the answers provided, we were able to draw some conclusions regarding the decisive factors in procurement decisions and the authorities and rights in the respective countries. It also became clear that the innovative procurement methods and procedures are still not common in the member states,

Annexes

Annexe 1: Questionnaire about the educational technology procurement in countries of the LEA Consortium

Annex 1: Questionnaire about the educational technology procurement in countries of the LEA Consortium

* 1. In which country are you situated?

* 2. What is the type of your organization/institution?

* 3. Do the primary/secondary schools have right to decide what kind of educational technology tool to purchase?

Other (please specify)

* 4. If the school does not have right, which institution/organization is responsible for the decision about the procurement of educational technology?

* 5. Does the decision making organization/procurer think that it would hinder the procurement process if the schools would have decision making right?

Yes

No

Other (please specify)

* 6. Please indicate how important are the following factors in making decision about which technology will be purchased for primary/secondary schools? (1- not important at all, 4- extremely important)

	Not important at all	Slightly important	Important	Extremely important
Price	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>			
Time saved for teachers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>			
Compatibility with already used systems, softwares	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>			
Technology is beyond state of the art	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>			
Teachers already have got the necessary skills for using the technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>			
Technology is combined with trainings that help to use it	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>			
Opinion of the school/teachers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="text"/>			

* 7. Is there any specified budget for purchasing educational technology?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

* 8. What is the main financial source for educational technology procurement?

- Own source
- EU Grants
- National Grants
- Sponsors' financial support
- Other (please specify)

* 9. Was there any Pre-Commercial Procurement implemented in your country that you know of?

- Yes
- No

10. If there was, in which sector?

- Agriculture
- Education
- Energy
- Other (please specify)
- Health
- Public administration

